

**SILENCING GLYCINE DECARBOXYLASE COMPLEX P-PROTEIN IN RICE
(*Oryza sativa* L.) MESOPHYLL CELLS USING ARTIFICIAL MICRORNA**

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The thesis attached hereto, entitled “**SILENCING GLYCINE DECARBOXYLASE COMPLEX P-PROTEIN IN RICE (*Oryza sativa* L.) MESOPHYLL CELLS USING ARTIFICIAL MICRORNA**” prepared by **CHRISTIAN PAOLO B. BALAHADIA**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **MASTER OF SCIENCE (MOLECULAR BIOLOGY AND BIOTECHNOLOGY)** is hereby accepted.

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ABSTRACT

BALAHADIA, CHRISTIAN PAOLO B., University of the Philippines Los Baños, June 2017, Silencing Glycine Decarboxylase Complex P-Protein in Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) Mesophyll Cells Using Artificial microRNA.

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Photorespiration or C_2 cycle is the process of neutralizing the toxic metabolite byproducts of RuBP oxygenation by Rubisco. Rice is a C_3 plant that lose yield from the release of CO_2 by the glycine decarboxylase complex (GDC) and expenditure of energy due to photorespiration. Examination of extant C_3 - C_4 intermediates species has shown that GDC P-protein (GDPC) expression evolved to exclusively express in the bundle sheath cells and no longer in the mesophyll cells. This formed the CO_2 concentrating mechanism called C_2 photosynthesis which minimized photorespiration. This study was able to knockdown the expression of GDPC in the mesophyll cells using artificial microRNA driven by maize PEP carboxylase promoter. GDPC protein expression in the leaves was reduced into undetectable levels in western blot. Transgenic plants display classical photorespiratory impaired mutant phenotype, which suffers from chlorosis and early senescence when exposed in ambient air however recovers when placed in high CO_2 condition. This also supported by the high accumulation of glycine and altered carbohydrate content. Physiological analysis of photosynthesis showed increase in CO_2 compensation point, and photoinhibition in ambient air. This study is the first of its kind to show that significant reduction of GDPC in the leaves will produce severe photorespiratory phenotype.

Key Words: Glycine Decarboxylase Complex, P-Protein, Photorespiration, C_2 photosynthesis, artificial microRNA

INTRODUCTION

United Nations estimates that in the year 2050, as much as 10 billion people will inhabit this planet and much of this increase would be coming from developing countries (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2015). Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is considered as one of the staple crops in the world. Through decades of research plant breeders have been successful in harnessing rice genetic diversity, leading to the release of a number of high yielding varieties. However, in recent years, rice yield have not increased considerably and current estimates does not seem to show a change in this trend (Khush, 2000). It is predicted that conventional breeding practices alone will not be able to cope with the rise in yield needed by the projected demand and the ever changing climate of the future (Covshoff and Hibberd, 2012). One of the major factors that could potentially increase yield is by engineering more efficient photosynthetic carbon assimilation in rice, which would not only increase biomass, but will improve water and nitrogen use efficiency. An example of an efficient type of photosynthesis is called C₄ photosynthesis which can be found in nature's most productive crops such as maize and sorghum. This C₄ syndrome has evolved independently 66 times within the plant kingdom since they started oxygenic photosynthesis (Sage et al., 2012). Although it seemed to be a ubiquitous trait across the plant kingdom it is not governed by a single gene rather it is a complex trait brought about by a number of biochemical enzymes, transporters, and regulatory genes that not only affect plant physiology but leaf anatomy as well (Sage et al., 2013). Evolution of these complex traits may not have occurred in a

single adaptive event, but rather a series of evolutionary steps that is fine-tuned by environmental selective pressures (Heckmann et al., 2013; Williams et al., 2013). Though it seems to be a daunting task to engineer a complex trait, the pace in which biotechnology have advanced today provides new and exciting ways to attempt installing it and learn from this endeavor (Schuler et al., 2016).

Photosynthesis provides the majority of the production of all organic compounds essential to life by fixing the inorganic carbon (CO_2) from the air using the light energy from the sun. This process is primarily done by the Ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate (RuBP) Carboxylase/Oxygenase (Rubisco) enzyme. Rubisco is deemed as the most abundant protein in the planet found in every photosynthesizing organism and drives the carbon flow in the biosphere. The usefulness of Rubisco comes with a caveat that it is not only specific for fixing CO_2 but for O_2 as well. This was not a problem early on primitive earth where O_2 levels are not that significant to compete with the active site of Rubisco. But as photosynthesizing organisms flourish, the production of O_2 became progressively higher (Hagemann et al., 2016). The major drawback of fixing O_2 is the production of metabolites that greatly inhibits important enzymes in the photosynthetic pathway which causes toxicity in plants. In order to neutralize these toxic metabolites, organisms spend a considerable amount of energy as well as the release of initially fixed carbon and nitrogen. This essential but wasteful process persistently linked with photosynthesis is called photorespiration (Weber and Bauwe, 2013).

In the majority of plants, Rubisco initially fixes CO₂ into a five-carbon compound called RuBP thereby producing two three-carbon compound 3-phosphoglycerate (3PG), which some are then used to form new RuBP for another round of carboxylation (Calvin Cycle) hence they are called C₃ plants. In C₃ plants such as rice, Rubisco is present in all photosynthesizing tissues where both CO₂ and O₂ can compete for the active site of Rubisco. The oxygenation of the substrate RuBP produces one molecule of 3PG along with a two-carbon metabolite, 2-phosphoglycolate (2PG). Plants have inherited photorespiration from its cyanobacterial ancestors which provided a metabolic process to repurpose 2PG (Hagemann et al., 2016). Photorespiration, also known as the C₂ cycle, is the process of neutralizing the toxic two carbon 2-PG product of RuBP oxygenation into a useful three-carbon metabolite that can be used for another round of photosynthesis (Maurino and Peterhansel, 2010). Though it seems to be a wasteful process, photorespiration plays important roles in maintaining redox balance, one carbon and amino acid metabolism, and nitrate assimilation (Hodges et al., 2016). A great number of studies have supported the undeniable importance of the C₂ cycle to support plant life as it is highly integrated in several vital metabolic pathways. The importance of the C₂ cycle might have allowed it to persist in the plant kingdom through evolution with varying efficiencies.

Some plants have overcome the wasteful process of photorespiration by spatial separation of the initial CO₂ fixation and the Rubisco carboxylation which is called C₄ photosynthesis. When the atmospheric CO₂ enters the leaf, it is initially fixed to a three-carbon phosphoenol-pyruvate (PEP) forming a four-carbon metabolite oxaloacetate in the

mesophyll cells, due to the absence of Rubisco. Oxaloacetate is then converted into Malate which is later transported and decarboxylated in the bundle-sheath cells. The bundle-sheath cells form an isolated compartment where atmospheric oxygen cannot enter and compete with the active site of Rubisco, while CO₂ is enriched through the transport and decarboxylation of a four carbon metabolite. The major advantage of the C₄ pathway is its efficient way of partitioning the photosynthetic carbon fixation into two morphologically distinct cell types (mesophyll cell and bundle sheath cells) in the leaf with a certain arrangement known as Kranz anatomy. The result of this morphological and biochemical change is a unique carbon concentrating mechanism that minimizes photorespiration (Langdale, 2011).

In C₄ plants, photorespiration is very much reduced due to the isolation of Rubisco from the atmospheric oxygen. This allows plants to close their stomata for a longer period of time without suffering from increasing O₂ as CO₂ gets depleted during photosynthesis. This proves to be very beneficial and advantageous for C₄ plants since they can close their stomata in hot climates to minimize water loss due to transpiration (Wang et al., 2014). C₄ plants were classically characterized by their very low compensation points due to their insensitivity to O₂ (Vogan et al., 2007). Compensation point is a derived parameter obtained from leaf gas exchange measurement which is defined as the value of the intercellular CO₂ concentration wherein CO₂ assimilation is equal to rate of cellular respiration and photorespiration. In C₄ plants it is much closer to zero which simply means that they can still assimilate CO₂ in the presence of much higher O₂ concentration than CO₂. C₃ plants on the other hand has a much higher

compensation point than C_4 plants by as much as 40 times (Leegood, 2002; Tolbert et al., 1995). The compensation point also served as one of the parameters used to screen C_3 - C_4 intermediate species among genera that contain C_3 and C_4 species (Krenzer et al., 1975). C_3 - C_4 intermediate plants have compensation points between known C_3 and C_4 relatives, which became the focus of evolutionary studies to elucidate C_4 evolution (Monson et al., 1984; Sage et al., 2012).

Photorespiration is a complex pathway that encompasses four subcellular locations. It starts in the chloroplasts where 2PG is produced from the oxygenation of RuBP. 2PG is then dephosphorylated by phosphoglycolate phosphatase into glycolate and transported out of the chloroplast. Glycolate enters the peroxisome where it is oxidized by glycolate oxidase into glyoxylate. Both 2-PG and glyoxylate are potent inhibitors of photosynthetic enzymes such as phosphofructokinase and triose phosphate isomerase, and Rubisco activase, respectively (Anderson, 1971; Chastain and Ogren, 1989; Kelly and Latzko, 1976). Glyoxylate in the peroxisome is converted into glycine through transamination with either serine/glutamate/alanine. The inert amino acid glycine is transported into the mitochondria where it is acted upon by the glycine decarboxylase complex (GDC). Two molecules of glycine are consumed per reaction of GDC which produce serine with the concomitant release of CO_2 , NH_3 , and NADH. Serine is then exported out of the mitochondria, return to the peroxisome and deaminated by serine:glyoxylate aminotransferase producing hydroxypyruvate. Hydroxypyruvate is reduced into glycerate by hydroxypyruvate reductase in the peroxisome or the cytosol. The resulting glycerate is transported back into chloroplast where it is phosphorylated by

glycerate kinase into 3-phosphoglycerate, which can now enter the Calvin cycle to regenerate RuBP that completes the C₂ cycle (Peterhansel et al., 2010).

The glycine decarboxylase complex (GDC) is responsible for the net carbon loss caused by the C₂ cycle through the decarboxylation of glycine. Since the characterization of C₃-C₄ intermediate species it has been postulated that the improvement of their compensation point is due to the isolation of the GDC to the bundle sheath cells (Monson et al., 1984; Monson and Rawsthorne, 2000). Immunological and physiological analysis of the intermediate species proved that the GDC is indeed expressed only in the bundle sheath cells which increased the recapture of photorespired CO₂, that lead to the reduction of compensation point (Muhaidat et al., 2011; Sage et al., 2012). The isolation of GDC in the bundle sheath cells of C₃-C₄ intermediate species was one of the hallmark traits that distinguish the group from its C₃ and C₄ relatives (Bauwe and Kolukisaoglu, 2003; Khoshravesh et al., 2016).

GDC is a multi-subunit protein complex composed of four proteins namely the P, T, L, and H subunits (Douce et al., 2001). The P-subunit is the main decarboxylating enzyme which releases CO₂ from glycine and transfers the remaining amino-methyl group onto the H-protein. The H-subunit acts as the amino-methyl group carrier through its lipoic acid moiety hence possess no enzymatic activity. The T-protein transfers the amino-methyl group from the H-protein onto tetrahydrofolate (THF) producing N⁵-N¹⁰ methylene-THF with a concomitant release of ammonia. The L-protein oxidizes the reduced H-protein with the aid of FADH₂ liberating NADH in the process. Among the

four proteins of the complex, P-protein (GDCP) is believed to have exclusive metabolic role, while the other three are postulated to interact with other metabolic pathways in the mitochondria (Bauwe, 2011). Though the subunits are not tightly linked, the presence of all the subunits is needed for its catalytic activity (Engel et al., 2007). Immunogold labeling of GDCP in C_3 plants, showed expression is present in both mesophyll and bundle sheath cells, while in C_4 plants, it is only found in the bundle sheath cells (Rawsthorne et al., 1988; Yoshimura et al., 2004).

In the genus *Flaveria*, there is a great variety of C_3 , C_3 - C_4 intermediate, C_4 -like, and true C_4 species. Studies on the genus revealed that the GDCP found in the C_4 species evolved through a change in a *cis* regulatory element that isolated its expression in the bundle sheath cells (Schulze et al., 2013). Rubisco is still present in the mesophyll cells of the intermediate species and oxygenation of RuBP occur in similar rates as in C_3 species though the concomitant glycine produced are no longer decarboxylated in the mesophyll cells. The increase in glycine concentrations in the mesophyll cells would efflux into the bundle sheath cells where it would be decarboxylated by GDC in the bundle sheath cells increasing the chance of CO_2 recapture by Rubisco. The phenomenon in which the GDC relocation to the bundle sheath cell acts as carbon concentrating mechanism in C_3 - C_4 intermediate species is termed as C_2 photosynthesis (Vogan et al., 2007). Further transcriptome comparisons of the various species in *Flaveria* revealed that C_2 photosynthesis function as a pre-adaptation for the evolution of the C_4 syndrome, through the observed increase in expression of C_4 cycle enzymes with the increase in C_2 cycle enzymes in the intermediate species (Mallmann et al., 2014).

This study aimed to understand the effect of knocking down the GDC in mesophyll cells as precursor to moving the GDC to the bundle sheath cells as seen in C₂ photosynthesis. This was done by knocking down the GDCP through the use of artificial microRNA (amiRNA) as a means of post transcriptional gene silencing method to control its gene expression in the mesophyll cells. To ensure tissue specific knockdown in the mesophyll cells, the previously reported maize PEP-carboxylase promoter was used to drive mesophyll cell – specific gene expression in rice (Matsuoka et al., 1994). This approach was designed in order to have a strong and high specificity gene silencing in order to isolate glycine decarboxylation in the rice bundle sheath cells (Warthmann et al., 2008). Here, the effects or consequences on rice photosynthesis and physiology by knocking down the expression of GDCP in its mesophyll cells were investigated. The possibility of installing C₂ photosynthesis in C₃ plant architecture as a precursor for establishing C₄ photosynthesis was explored as well.

Objectives of the Study

The study has three specific objectives:

- 1.) To design and construct artificial microRNA (amiGDGP) that would target the glycine decarboxylase P-protein (GDGP) genes in rice;
- 2.) To generate GDGP knockdown plants through *Agrobacterium* - mediated transformation of amiGDGP constructs into wild type IR64 rice;
- 3.) To characterize the molecular and physiological effects of GDGP knockdown in stable transgenic lines.

This study was conducted at the C4 Rice Center and the Genetic Transformation Laboratories at IRRI from January 2014 to August 2015, under the guidance of Dr. Hsiang-Chun Lin of the Transgenic Physiology Team and Dr. Shanta Karki of the Genetic Engineering Team.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Photorespiration and C₄ photosynthesis evolution

There has been a lot of attention paid to photorespiration since its discovery due to its effect on photosynthetic efficiency. Summary of the C₂ cycle gene knockout mutants found in *Arabidopsis* all points to its importance for plant survival in oxygenic atmosphere (Timm and Bauwe, 2013). Apart from the research done in *Arabidopsis*, studies on non-model crops also points to the importance of the C₂ cycle not only to photosynthesis but in various primary metabolic pathways that sustain life in plants (Ferne et al., 2013; Hodges et al., 2016). Nevertheless, the undeniable losses in crop yield due to photorespiration alone still warrants effort towards its research to increase its efficiency. A regional scale analysis of yield losses in C₃ crops, soybean and wheat, estimates a 36% and 20% decrease annually due to photorespiration, respectively (Walker et al., 2016). It is also predicted that the removal of photorespiration effect on yield would give rise to 12-55% increase in gross photosynthesis even with the adverse effects of future climate change and increase in atmospheric CO₂ (Walker et al., 2016). One of the most efficient strategies to minimize photorespiration and a product of 40 million years of evolution is C₄ photosynthesis (Sage et al., 2012).

C₄ photosynthesis was first discovered by Hatch & Slack in 1966 on sugarcane leaves. Through radioactive labeled CO₂ feeding experiments, Hatch and Slack were able

to show that CO₂ in sugarcane leaves is primarily fixed to four carbon compounds, such as malate, aspartate, and oxaloacetate, instead to the canonical 3-PGA as a result of Calvin-Benson-Bassham cycle or C₃ cycle. C₃ plants have a complete C₃ cycle and C₂ cycle operating in both mesophyll and bundle sheath cells (Fig. 1). C₄ plants have managed to isolate the C₃ cycle in the bundle sheath cells away from atmospheric oxygen, while an adjacent mesophyll cell is the one exposed to air and captures CO₂ into four carbon compounds (Fig. 2C). The four carbon metabolite is then transferred into the bundle sheath cells through the plasmodesmata and decarboxylated in the chloroplast. This tandem function of the bundle sheath cells and mesophyll cell around leaf vein is characterized as Kranz anatomy. This unique carbon concentrating mechanism is very efficient and complex but surprisingly evolved from C₃ plants more than 60 times independently, a great example of convergent evolution (Sage et al., 2012).

It is postulated that the complex trait of C₄ photosynthesis did not happen in a single genetic event rather it was more likely to have been modular and in a series of adaptive steps with each step landmarked by intermediary states (Heckmann et al., 2013). The discovery of extant C₃-C₄ intermediates among genera that contains C₃ and C₄ species paved the way to the understanding of the possible transitory states that enable the evolution of C₄ photosynthesis from C₃ plants (Edwards and Ku, 1987; Kennedy and Laetsch, 1974). Some of the distinguishing anatomical features of C₃-C₄ intermediates is the establishment of a Kranz-like anatomy and increased in number of chloroplast and mitochondria in the bundle sheath cells (Sage et al., 2014). Apart from anatomical features, C₃-C₄ intermediates were also identified by their compensation point (Γ) which

lies in-between the C₃ and C₄ values. C₃ plants have compensation point in the range of 40-50 μL/L intercellular CO₂, while C₄ plants have close to zero values. The C₃-C₄ intermediates on the other hand lies in a spectrum between the C₃ and C₄ values, with some C₄-like species having 1-5 μL/L but mostly 20-40 μL/L (Edwards and Ku, 1987). The intermediate nature of their compensation point and O₂ insensitivity indicates a possible CO₂ concentrating mechanism to recapture the photorespired CO₂. Even early on the research of C₃-C₄ intermediates, it was thought that glycine shuttling from mesophyll cells to the bundle sheath cells is the most logical means of CO₂ concentrating mechanism (Monson et al., 1984). This hypothesis was easily proven by a number of studies on intermediate species using immunogold labeling of the GDCP subunit, in which all results point to the isolation of GDCP in the bundle sheath cells (Monson and Rawsthorne, 2000; Rawsthorne et al., 1988). The isolation of GDC in the bundle sheath cells which splits the C₂ cycle into two cell types was later on termed as C₂ photosynthesis (Fig. 2) (Vogan et al., 2007).

All of the genes found in C₄ cycle in C₄ species are also present in C₃ species, though they might have different function and expression in C₃ species but they are undeniably co-opted in the course of C₄ evolution (Sage et al., 2012; Schuler et al., 2016). Recent analysis on the eudicot *Flaveria*, which has the most number of intermediate species (10), as well as true C₃ and C₄ species, established that the isolation of GDC in the bundle sheath cells was due to a mutation at a *cis*-regulatory element in GDCP gene that was previously constitutively expressed in both mesophyll and bundle sheath cells (Sage et al., 2013; Schulze et al., 2013). Transcriptomic analysis of the leaves in various

species in *Flaveria* show that the increase in the C₄-ness of an intermediate species has a corresponding increase in the expression of the C₄ enzymes (Mallmann et al., 2014; Schulze et al., 2016). Similar study in C₃-C₄ intermediates in grasses show the same evolutionary trajectory as observed in eudicots (Khoshravesh et al., 2016). The changes in the anatomy (C₂-Kranz, refers to Kranz-like anatomy performing C₂ photosynthesis) of intermediary species was accompanied by the increase in expression or co-option of C₄ enzymes, which not only aid in the C₂ photosynthesis but also prevented the nitrogen imbalance that may result if only the GDC was isolated in the bundle sheath cells (Mallmann et al., 2014; Sage et al., 2014).

In retrospect, looking at the C₄ pathway (Figure 2) it may seem that the C₂ cycle does not have a role for its proper function in C₄ plants due to its efficient CO₂ concentrating mechanism, but it served an important role in the establishment of C₄ photosynthesis in C₃ plants. An important study in maize (C₄) of a homozygous knockout mutant in the C₂ cycle enzyme, Glycolate Oxidase I, exhibited seedling lethal phenotype when grown in ambient air. Seedlings were rescued when grown under high CO₂ condition (1%-5%) (Zelitch et al., 2009). The study have shown that even with the efficient CO₂ concentrating mechanism of C₄ plants they still depend on photorespiration throughout seedling development to neutralize the toxic glycolate accumulation (Zelitch et al., 2009).

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of photorespiration in plants. Photorespiration spans across the chloroplast, peroxisome and mitochondria. It starts with the oxygenation of RuBP (ribulose 1, 5-bis-phosphate) by Rubisco which produce 2-PG (2-phosphoglycolate). 2-PG will be dephosphorylated by phosphoglycolate phosphatase and exported out of the chloroplast; the resulting glycolate will be oxidized by glycolate oxidase in the peroxisome producing glyoxylate. The formation of glycine is a product of transamination from three possible amino acid donors: serine, glutamate (Glu), or alanine, by serine:glyoxylate aminotransferase (SGT) and glutamate:glyoxylate aminotransferase (GGT). Two glycine molecules will enter mitochondria and decarboxylated by the glycine decarboxylase complex (GDC) producing serine and a concomitant release of CO₂ and NH₃. Ammonia can be re-fixed in the chloroplast glutamine synthetase-glutamate synthase cycle (GS-GOGAT). The serine can enter the peroxisome to serve as amino donor to glyoxylate and produce hydroxypyruvate. Hydroxypyruvate can be reduced in the peroxisome or cytosol by hydroxypyruvate reductase yielding glycerate. Glycerate can enter the chloroplast and phosphorylated by glycerate kinase to produce 3-phosphoglycerate (3-PG) that can enter the Calvin cycle. The conversion of 2-PG to glycine and Serine to 3-PG were not elaborated and shown as dashed arrows. Reducing power or ATP released or consumed was not presented here (Bauwe, 2011).

Figure 2. C₂ photosynthesis in C₃-C₄ intermediates and C₄ photosynthesis.

Image adopted from Schulze et al. (2016) and Mallmann et al. (2014). (A) C₂ photosynthesis found in basic C₃-C₄ intermediate species by isolating the glycine

decarboxylation in the bundle sheath cells. While (B) shows C₂ photosynthesis in more advance C₃-C₄ intermediate species by having an increase in expression and co-option of C₄ biochemical genes. Whereas (C) demonstrates true C₄ photosynthesis shown to have lost Rubisco in the mesophyll cells and now isolated in the bundle sheath cells with minimal photorespiration. Abbreviations found in Figure 1 still applies for this figure, along with; AlaAT: Alanine aminotransferase; 2-OG: 2-oxoglutarate; Pyr: Pyruvate; PPK: Phosphoenol pyruvate dikinase; PEP: Phosphoenol pyruvate; PEPC: Phosphoenol pyruvate carboxylase; OAA: oxaloacetate; MDH: malate dehydrogenase; Mal: Malate; ME: Malic enzyme; Asp: Aspartate; AspAT: Aspartate aminotransferase.

Glycine Decarboxylase Complex

The glycine decarboxylase complex (GDC) also known as glycine cleavage system facilitates the oxidative decarboxylation and deamination of glycine as a product of photorespiration. It is composed of four protein subunits containing three enzymes, P-, T-and L-subunits, with different functions in the complex, along with the H-subunit that acts as a mobile substrate for the three enzymes through its lipoic acid moiety (Fig. 3). GDC is highly abundant in mitochondria of photosynthetic cells occupying half of the total protein content in the mitochondria. It has been shown that the mechanism and structure of the complex is conserved in plants, animals, and bacteria (Douce et al., 2001).

The H subunit is a 16 kD monomeric lipoamide-containing protein without enzymatic activity. It is believed to have a central role in GDC as it serves as a mobile substrate for the three enzymes in the complex. The P enzyme (E.C. 1.4.4.2) is a 200 kD

homodimer protein that contains a pyridoxal-5-phosphate and serves as the actual enzyme that decarboxylates the glycine molecule. The product of the reaction would result in the release of CO₂ and a transfer of the remaining amino methylene moiety to the sulfur atom of the H protein's lipoamide arm, forming a Schiff base. T enzyme (E.C. 2.1.2.10) is a 45 kD monomeric protein that catalyzes the aminomethyl transfer from the H protein to tetrahydrofolate (THF) which leads to the release of ammonia and production of N⁵,N¹⁰-methyleneTHF, leaving the H protein fully reduced. L enzyme (E.C. 1.8.1.4) is a 100 kD homodimer that has dihydrolipoamide dehydrogenase activity which re-oxidize the lipoamide moiety in H protein through a reduction of FAD to FADH₂ and subsequently re-oxidized by NAD⁺ producing NADH + H⁺ and then the glycine decarboxylase complex ready for another cycle of glycine cleavage. The L enzyme is also a part of the α -ketoacid dehydrogenases as the E3 subunit (Bauwe and Kolukisaoglu, 2003). The production of N⁵,N¹⁰-methyleneTHF in the cycle made most scientists believe that the complex plays an important role in one carbon metabolism (Peterhansel et al., 2010).

The role of GDC in photorespiration has been well established (Peterhansel et al., 2010). Different C₄ type plants such as *Zea mays* (NADP-ME), *Panicum miliaceum* (NAD-ME), and *Panicum maximum* (PEP-CK) have been shown to lack the GDC activity in the mesophyll cells of mature green leaves due to the absence of the GDC subunits in these cells. However, mesophyll cells of etiolated leaves from these samples expresses GDCH and Rubisco small subunit and both are lost after leaf maturation. The Rubisco and GDC are both active and present in mesophyll cells and bundle sheath cell

of C₃ plants while they are only present in the bundles sheath cells of the C₄ plants. That is why it has been hypothesized that the mechanism of suppression is the same for Rubisco small subunit and GdcH protein (Parys and Jastrzebski, 2008).

The GDC is inhibited by the victorin toxin from *Cochliobolus victoriae* known as the Victoria blight in oats which acts by binding specifically to P-enzyme and the H-protein to elicit enzyme inhibition (Navarre and Wolpert, 1995).

Over-expression experiment of the H and L proteins in *Arabidopsis thaliana* resulted in higher photosynthetic rate, lower CO₂ compensation point, higher biomass, larger and higher number of leaves compared to wild type which demonstrates that C₂ cycle enhances photosynthesis (Timm et al., 2012; 2015). The increase in the photosynthetic capacity of the overexpressing lines supports the positive feedback effect of having a high C₂ cycle activity that efficiently removes the negative inhibitors of the Calvin cycle, hence the better performance of the transgenic lines. This evidence also support the function and necessity of an existing C₂ cycle in C₄ plants and they have devised more than one CO₂ concentrating mechanism in order to efficiently saturate the Rubisco in the bundle sheath cells (Timm et al., 2015).

Several approaches were also considered to bypass the photorespiration by engineering plants with cyanobacterial enzymes that would metabolize and decarboxylate the glyoxylate at the chloroplast that would provide an alternative CO₂ concentrating mechanism near Rubisco (Maurino et al., 2012). Another approach was done by inserting

enzymes from *E. coli* to create an alternative pathway of glyoxylate metabolism to prevent its decarboxylation altogether. This approach produced higher biomass but only in restricted environmental condition and photosynthetic parameters were still the same (Carvalho et al., 2011; Maier et al., 2012).

Figure 3. The glycine decarboxylase system. Also known as glycine cleavage system as it separates the functional groups of glycine to give off CO_2 , NH_3 , and $\text{N}^5, \text{N}^{10}$ -methyleneTHF. The first reaction entails the formation of Schiff base between pyridoxal phosphate (PLP) and glycine catalyzed by the P enzyme which also catalyzes the decarboxylation of glycine and transfer of the methylamine to the lipoic arm of the H protein. The T enzyme will now catalyze the release of ammonia and the transfer of the remaining carbon to tetrahydrofolate. The process reduces the lipoic residue of H protein which will be acted upon by the L enzyme by transferring electron to NADH and preparing the system for the next cycle. Image was obtained from Lehninger Principles of Biochemistry, 4th ed (Nelson & Cox, 2005).

P-Subunit of Glycine Decarboxylase Complex

The P-subunit of glycine decarboxylase complex also known as the “glycine decarboxylase” performs the actual decarboxylation of glycine in the multi-enzyme complex (Bauwe et al., 2010). Rice has two isoforms of GDCP (Os01g51410 and Os06g40940) that are highly expressed in leaves and minimal expression in non-photosynthetic tissues (Engel et al., 2007). Rice being a C3 plant has most of the expression seen in the leaves which is attributed to high photorespiratory activity for it to survive in ambient air.

Arabidopsis thaliana, a C3 plant as well, has also two GDCP isoforms. The individual T-DNA knockout mutant of the GDCP in *Arabidopsis* does not significantly alter metabolism and photosynthetic performance. However, combined T-DNA mutants do not produce rosette leaves and seedlings do not survive for longer than three to four weeks (Engel et al., 2007). The results of the combined knockout mutant of the GDCP genes in *Arabidopsis* indicate that it provides the same function for the C2 cycle (complementary function) and it is also needed for vital metabolic processes other than the C2 cycle (Engel et al., 2007).

RNA silencing approach was done in potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) using antisense technology driven by the mesophyll specific promoter of the C4 plant *Flaveria pringlei* GDCP and another study using potato ST-LS1 promoter from a gene that is expressed as

a part of photosystem 2 (Heineke and Bauwe, 2001; Heineke et al., 2001). The resulting transgenic plants have as much as 60-70% reduction in GDCP in the leaves. The mild knockdown did not demonstrate classical photorespiratory impaired phenotype which is lethal in ambient air but can be rescued in high CO₂ condition, though high glycine accumulation was observed during the day compared to wild type (Heineke et al., 2001). A follow up study by Bykova et al. (2005) found that GDCP knockdown lines showed increase in respiratory decarboxylation in the light to compensate for the imbalance of reducing power and energy caused by the impaired C2 cycle.

GDCH mutants found in sodium azide mutagenized population of barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) exhibited the classical photorespiratory impaired phenotype (Blackwell et al., 1988). Homozygous lines from the said mutant were generated and showed that the reduction of the H-subunit produces a similar reduction in the P-subunit protein expression (Wingler et al., 1997). This parallel reduction in GDCP expression was also observed in rice when amiRNA was used to knockdown the most abundant isoform of GDCH in rice leaves using mesophyll specific promoter (Lin et al., 2016). The barley GDCP knockdown line showed unperturbed expression of the GDCH regardless of the amount of knockdown in GDCP (Blackwell et al., 1990). The one-way dependence of the GDCP expression on GDCH might indicate that GDCH has other roles in plant metabolism apart from photorespiration (Timm and Bauwe, 2013). Severe photorespiratory impaired phenotype was observed in rice when double stranded RNAi driven by maize ubiquitin promoter was used to target GDCH (Zhou et al., 2013). The added severity in the GDCH knockdown lines observed in the study by Zhou et al. (2013)

might have been due constitutive nature of the promoter used in silencing (Lin et al., 2016).

amiRNA Silencing

Micro RNAs (miRNA) are a class of endogenous small RNA that specifically target a gene or a group of genes through complementation that leads to transcriptional or translational inhibition, such as mRNA cleavage in plants (Arikiti et al., 2013). Figure 7 shows the diagram of miRNA biosynthesis. MiRNAs are usually 21 nucleotides long with 2-3 mismatches from its intended gene target. The site of complementation is also the site of the cleavage which is mostly located at the 3' end of the coding region as well as the 3' untranslated region (UTR) (Ossowski et al., 2008)

Artificial microRNA (amiRNA) makes use of the natural miRNA machinery to enable cleavage-mediated transcript degradation of specific gene (or group of genes) of interest by mimicking all the features of endogenous miRNAs. AmiRNAs have been tested in several plant species such as *Arabidopsis* and rice, that gave gene specific silencing of intended target using the native miRNA backbones of the respective organisms (Schwab et al., 2006a; Warthmann et al., 2013). Studies have shown that this technique is more accurate than hairpin RNAi technique in targeting specific genes (Chen, 2012) with limited non-cell-autonomous effects (Warthmann et al., 2013).

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of miRNA mediated gene silencing. A non-coding RNA is transcribed from the micro RNA genes which will become the primary-miRNA. The pri-miRNA will then undergo a series of folding until it reaches the correct secondary structure. The pri-miRNA will be recognized by the Dicer Like 1 (DCL1) nuclease and cleave the stem and loop region of the transcript to become a precursor miRNA (hair-pins) and eventually become a duplex miRNA. The duplex is 21 bp dsRNA that contains the miRNA sequence which complementary to the target sequence to be silenced. The complementary sequence to the miRNA duplex is called miRNA* which displays a mismatch at the 5' end that induces instability that helps in recognizing the correct transcript to use for silencing. The miRNA will bind with the Argonaute protein that interacts with the RNA-induced Silencing Complex (RISC) which catalyzes the cleavage of the target sequence. (Arikiti et al., 2013; Ding et al., 2012)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The bulk of this research was conducted in the C4 Rice Center Lab and the Genetic Transformation Lab at IRRI with the exception of the leaf amino-acid content analysis, in which freeze dried samples were shipped to University of Sheffield (Department of Animal and Plant Sciences, Mass Spectrometry Facility) in UK for the HPLC analysis.

The general experimental workflow of this research can be described as follows; two amiRNA gene constructs to target GDPCP genes in rice were designed and constructed; the constructs were transformed into rice; gene insertion was verified and lines with good gene silencing were selected; candidate lines were advanced to T₁ generation; T₁ lines were grown in high and ambient CO₂ environment conditions; gene expression analysis was performed; photosynthetic rates were measured and metabolite analysis on T₁ lines with different environmental treatments was performed. The experiment workflow is illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Experiment work flow of the study. Parts lined in red, blue, and orange highlights the steps made to answer the three main objectives respectively.

Generation of amiGDCP Constructs

amiGDCP Design

Artificial microRNA was used to silence the two endogenous GDCP genes in *Oryza sativa* (Os01g51410 and Os06g40940). The tools in the WMD3 website (<http://wmd3.weigelworld.org/>) were used to design the 21 nucleotide amiRNA and amiRNA* sequences that would target GDCP genes following the guidelines discussed by Warthmann et al. (2013).

An existing amiRNA construct (IRS499) designed and created by Dr. Sarah Covshoff (Cambridge University, UK) was used as the template for the construction of the amiGDCP construct. The template construct contains an amiRNA gene driven by a mesophyll cell specific promoter from maize phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase (ZmPEPC) and a nopaline synthase (NOS) terminator from *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. This construct contains kanamycin resistance gene for selection during bacterial transformation while it does not contain a plant selectable marker for plant transformation (Fig. 9).

Fusion PCR

Fusion PCR was performed using six primers in order to replace the two 21 nucleotide amiRNA/amiRNA* sequences from IRS499 with the new amiRNA/amiRNA*

sequence generated using the WMD3 tools that would target GDCP genes. Figure 10A shows the positions of the six different primers in the amiRNA gene where primer L is located in the ZmPEPC promoter region while primer R is located in the NOS terminator both flanking the amiRNA gene. Primers I and II contains the new amiRNA sequence while primers III and IV contains the new amiRNA* sequence. Four sets of PCR reactions were done to amplify the new amiRNA gene using KAPA HiFi DNA polymerase (Kapa Biosystems, USA) following manufacturer's protocol. The PCR cycling profiles were 92°C for 2 min; 35 cycles of 95°C for 30s, 55°C for 30s, 72°C for 30s; 72°C for 7 min for PCR A, B, and C while 92°C for 2 min; 35 cycles of 95°C for 30s, 55°C for 30s, 72°C for 1 min; 72°C for 7 min for PCR D. PCR A, B, and C make use of the IRS499 plasmid as template with different sets of primers (primer L and primer II for PCR A, primer I and primer IV for PCR B, and primer III and Primer R for PCR C) to amplify different segments of the gene with the PCR products containing overlapping sequences. The PCR product sizes were verified by running in 2% agarose gel electrophoresis and the correct PCR products were extracted from the gel using Qiagen Gel Extraction Kit (Qiagen, USA) following manufacturer's protocol. The PCR products from PCR A and C were diluted ten times (1:10) while PCR B was diluted two folds (1:1) then were mixed in one cocktail that served as the template for PCR D (Fig. 10A). The PCR product of PCR D was run in 2% agarose gel to verify the correct size and extracted from the gel. The list of all the primers used in the study is found in Table 1.

Table 1. List of all primers and their corresponding sequences used in the cloning, transgene PCR screening, and gene expression analysis in the study.

Primer name	Primer Sequence	Product Size	Purpose
GDCP.1 I miR-F	AGTTTGAGATTAGAGCATGACAGCAGGAGATTCAGTTTGA- 3		
GDCP.1 II miR-R	TGCTGTCATGCTCTAATCTCAAACCTGCTGCTACAGCC- 3		Primers used for the construction of IRS896
GDCP.1 III miR*F	CTCTGTCTTGCACTAATCTCAAATTCCTGCTGCTAGGCTG- 3		
GDCP.1 IV miR*R	AATTTGAGATTAGTGCAAGACAGAGAGAGGCAAAAGTGAA- 3		
GDCP.2 I miR-F	AGTAATGCTAGTCAATAAAGCTCCAGGAGATTCAGTTTGA- 3		
GDCP.2 II miR-R	TGGAGCTTTATTGACTAGCATTACTGCTGCTGCTACAGCC- 3		Primers used for the construction of IRS897
GDCP.2 III miR*F	CTGAGCTATATAGACTAGCATTATTCTGCTGCTAGGCTG- 3		
GDCP.2 IV miR*R	AATAATGCTAGTCTATATAGCTCAGAGAGGCAAAAGTGAA- 3		
amiRNA-F (Primer L)	CTAACAGCAGCAAGCCAA- 3	816	Primer used for fusion PCR
amiRNA-R (Primer R)	GTAAAACGACGGCCAGT- 3		
GDCP-F	CAGTATGATCCCTCTTGGTTCT- 3	940	Os06g40940 and Os01g51410 gene specific primers
GDCP-R	GGCAACAGTTCCATTGACTC- 3		
amiGDCP.1pr-F	AGACACCCCTCTCCACAT- 3	417	PEPC promoter specific primer compatible with amiGDCP.1-R
amiGDCP.1-R	CTCCTGCTGTCATGCTCTAATCTCAAA- 3		IRS896 specific primer
amiGDCP.2pr-F	CTAACAGCAGCAAGCCAAGCC- 3	393	PEPC promoter specific primer compatible with amiGDCP.2-R
amiGDCP.2-R	CTGAATCTCCTGGAGCTTTATTGACTAGC- 3		IRS897 specific primer
GDCP 1.6-1F	AAGTGAAAGCAAGGCCGAAC- 3	162	Os06g40940 and Os01g51410 (GDCP isoforms) genes specific primers for qPCR
GDCP 1.6-1R	GGCTTAGTCCATGAGTCGCT- 3		
GDCP1-RT-F	CCTCAAGAGTGCTCCTCACC – 3	158	Os01g51410 (GDCP isoform1) gene specific primers for qPCR
GDCP1-RT-R	GGTTGCGATCCCCATACACA – 3		
GDCP2-RT-F	TGAATGCTCAGAAACACTACCCA - 3	223	Os06g40940 (GDCP isoform2) gene specific primers for qPCR
GDCP2-RT-R	AGTTCGGCCTTGCTTCACT – 3		
OSGDCH-RT-1F	ATTGGCAACGTGGAGAGTGTA- 3	81	OS10G0516100 (GDCH isoform1) gene specific primer
OSGDCH-RT-1R	TTGTCGTTAACCTCGACGACCTCA- 3		
GAPDH-NW-F	CTGCAACTCAGAAGACCGTTG- 3	329	Os04g0486600 (Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase) gene specific primer
GAPDH-NW-R	CCTGTTGTCACCCTGGAAGTC- 3		
EF1-e-3F	CCACTGGTGGTTTTGAGGC – 3	285	Os03g08010 (Elongation factor 1-alpha) gene specific primer
EF1-e-3R	GGCCCTTGTACCAGTCAAG – 3		

Restriction and Ligation of PCR products into the expression vector

The resulting PCR product from PCR D (816 bp) and the IRS499 plasmid (8627 bp) were independently double digested with *Bst*EII-HF (New England Biolabs, USA) and *Hind*III-HF (New England Biolabs, USA) following manufacturer's protocol. The digested products were run in 2% agarose gel alongside their undigested sample as negative control to verify if the fragments have the correct size. The 734 bp fragment (insert) from PCR D and 7560 bp fragment (backbone) from IRS499 plasmid were extracted from the gel (Fig. 10B). The concentrations of the digestion products were measured using Nanodrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher, USA). The ligation reaction was done using T4 DNA Ligase (Invitrogen Life Technologies, USA) following manufacturer's protocol with 78 ng of IRS499 fragment and 22 ng of PCR D fragment.

***E. coli* Transformation**

The ligation products were transformed into *E. coli* DH5 α chemically competent cells using heat shock method. Two microliters of the ligation product were added into DH5 α competent cells, mixed gently and placed on ice for 30 mins. The cells were heat shocked by incubating in 42°C for 45 seconds then placed on ice for two minutes. After the heat shock treatment, the cells were added with 950 μ L of LB broth and incubated in 37°C for 90 minutes. The bacterial suspension in LB broth was precipitated by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 3 min then 800 μ L of supernatant was removed. The remaining solution was plated in LB agar plate with kanamycin (50 mg/L) and incubated

at 37°C overnight. Single colonies formed were verified using PCR with primer L and primer R. Positive colonies were cultured in LB broth with kanamycin (50 mg/L) for plasmid isolation and further verification.

Figure 9. Plasmid map of the IRS499 construct used as template to create amiRNA that would target glycine decarboxylase complex P subunit (GDCP) genes in rice (A). (B) Schematic diagram of the amiRNA gene used to silence genes expressed in mesophyll cells.

A.

B.

Figure 10. Fusion PCR strategy to replace the two 21 nucleotide amiRNA/amiRNA* (red segments) sequences in IRS499 using four PCR reactions (A). Restriction and Ligation strategy to insert the new amiRNA fragment into the IRS499 template backbone (B).

Plasmid Isolation and Sequence Verification

The plasmids from the positive colonies grown in LB broth with kanamycin were isolated using Qiagen Plasmid Mini Kit (Qiagen, USA) following manufacturer's protocol. The concentration of the plasmids was obtained using Nanodrop spectrophotometer and the quality was verified by running 100 ng in 1% agarose gel. Three independent plasmids from different colonies were sent to MACROGEN (Korea) for DNA sequencing using primer L and primer R as sequencing primers. Plasmids with correct sequence were also digested with *KpnI* (New England Biolabs, USA) which was a double cutter for the new plasmid construct to verify the size of the plasmid.

Generation of Transgenic Plants

***Agrobacterium* Transformation**

The sequence verified plasmids were transformed into chemically competent *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* LBA 4404 using the freeze thaw method. One microgram of plasmid DNA was added to the LBA 4404 competent cells then placed on ice for a minute. The cells were freeze shocked by placing the solution in liquid Nitrogen for five min then placed at 37°C for five min. The culture was added with one milliliter of YEP (Yeast Extract Peptone) media and incubated for three to four hours at 28°C. The cultures were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for three min and the supernatant was removed and

replaced with 100 μ L of fresh YEP media and then mixed. The resulting suspension was plated in YEP agar plate containing kanamycin (50 mg/L) and incubated at 28°C for two days. Formed colonies were further purified by streaking into fresh YEP agar plate with kanamycin (50 mg/L). The resistant colonies were grown in YEP media with kanamycin (50 mg/L) and the plasmid DNA were isolated as mentioned above. The isolated plasmid from the *Agrobacterium* was re-transformed back into *E. coli* cells to verify again using PCR to check if the inserted plasmid was correct.

Another *Agrobacterium* bearing the pCAMBIA 1300 vector was also grown. This plasmid is an empty vector with sequence found in Genbank with ID AF234296.1. It contains a hygromycin resistance gene which was used to co-transform with the amiGDCP constructs since they do not contain any selectable marker.

Plant Transformation and Verification

Rice transformation was done using the protocol described by Hiei & Komari (2006). Rice immature embryos were used as explants that will undergo co-transformation with *Agrobacterium* infection solution bearing amiGDCP construct and *Agrobacterium* infection solution bearing hygromycin resistance gene as a co-transformation vector. The two constructs were mixed in 1:1 volume ratio. The immature embryos were co-cultivated with *Agrobacterium* and the resulting calli had undergone a series of transfer in selection medium containing 50 mg/L Hygromycin B. The

hygromycin resistant calli were transferred into regenerating medium to produce the T₀ generation transgenic plantlets.

The presence of amiRNA construct in the T₀ plants was verified using direct tissue PCR technique using TerraTM kit (Clontech, Takara Bio Group, Japan) following manufacturer's protocol. Since co-transformation was used it was necessary to perform PCR verification of the resulting transgenic plants to ensure that the amiGDCP gene was present in the hygromycin resistant plants. Primers specific to the 21 bp amiRNA was used as reverse primer while a compatible forward primer located in the ZmPEPC promoter was used to screen the transgenic plants since both sequences are absent in the wild type rice.

T-DNA Copy Number Analysis

Southern blotting technique was done to assess the T-DNA copy number of the T₀ transgenic plants. Genomic DNA was isolated from the one to two penultimate leaf tissues and extracted using the potassium acetate protocol described by Guillemaut and Maréchal-Drouard (1992). DNA quantity was measured using Nanodrop spectrophotometer and the quality was assessed by running 2 µg of DNA in 1.2% gel electrophoresis. Ten to twelve (10-12) µg of DNA samples were digested using *Hind*III or *Afl*III (New England Biolabs, USA) at 37°C for 12-16 hrs. The digested samples were separated using 0.8% agarose gel electrophoresis with 1X TAE buffer at 30 volts, overnight. DIG-labeled molecular weight markers (Roche Diagnostics, Germany) was

used to determine the apparent molecular size of the bands and plasmid DNA of the construct was also digested and loaded in the gel to serve as positive control. The gel was depurinated using 0.25 M HCl for 10 mins, denaturated using 0.5 M NaOH in 1.5 M NaCl for 15 min twice, and lastly neutralized using 0.5 M Tris (pH 7.5) in 1.5 M NaCl. DNA from the gel were transferred into Hybond Nylon+ membrane (GE Healthcare, UK) using capillary method and neutral transfer buffer using 20X SSC (0.3 M tri-sodium citrate acetate dihydrate, pH 7.0, in 3 M NaCl). The blots were hybridized with probe synthesized using PCR DIG Probe Synthesis Kit (Roche Diagnostics, Germany) with primers specific to the ZmPEPC promoter. Hybridization was done at 42°C overnight using homemade pre-hybridization buffer (5X SSC, 2% non-fat dry milk, 50% deionized formamide, 0.3% SDS, 22% maleic acid buffer). The blots were washed with 0.1% SDS in 2X SSC buffer for 20 min twice at room temperature, then 0.1% SDS in 0.1X SSC buffer for 10 min, for four times at 68°C. The blots were equilibrated with maleic acid buffer (0.1 M maleic acid, pH 7.5, in 0.15 M NaCl) for five min before placing in the blocking buffer (1% non-fat dry milk in maleic acid buffer) for 30 min. Anti-DIG Fab Fragment-AP conjugate (Roche Diagnostics, Germany) was used to detect the DIG labeled probe by adding 5 µL to the blot in the blocking buffer and incubated for 30 min. The excess Anit-DIG was washed using maleic acid for 20 min twice. The blots were detected using CDP-Star Detection Reagent (Roche Diagnostics, Germany) following manufacturers protocols.

Molecular and Physiological Verification of GDCP Knockdown Transgenic Plants

GDCP Transcript Analysis

Total RNA was extracted from PCR-positive T₀ plants from the youngest fully expanded leaf using TRIZOL reagent (Invitrogen, USA) following manufacturer's protocol. RNA quality was verified by running 2 µg of RNA in 2% agarose gel in 1X TAE. Total RNA was treated with RQ1 RNase free DNase (Promega, USA) to remove any residual genomic DNA contamination prior to cDNA synthesis using Transcriptor First Strand cDNA synthesis kit (Roche Diagnostics, Germany). The resulting cDNA sample was normalized to 100 ng/µL, to be used for quantitative PCR. qRT-PCR was done using 10 µL final reaction volume with 2 µL cDNA normalized sample, 1 µL of random hexamer primer, 1 µL of oligo-dT primer, and LightCycler 480 SybrGreen Master Mix I components (Roche Diagnostics, Germany). StepOnePlus Real-Time PCR System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) was used for the qPCR and the resulting data was analyzed using $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method described by Livak and Schmittgen (2001) to measure the relative abundance of the GDCP gene against wild type plants. The housekeeping gene used to normalize the expression of GDCP gene transcript in the study was either Glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH, LOC_Os04g40950) or Elongation Factor 1- α (EF1, LOC_Os03g08020).

Semi-quantitative Reverse Transcription PCR (sqRT-PCR) was used for initial transcript verification. *iTaq* DNA Polymerase (IntronBio, Korea) was used to amplify genes of interest following manufacturer's protocols. PCR products were loaded into 2% agarose gel with SYBR Safe DNA stain (Invitrogen, USA) and run in gel electrophoresis setup for one hour at 150V. The gel separated samples were viewed under Alliance UV gel documentation system (Uvitec Cambridge, UK). The resulting DNA bands on the image were analyzed densitometrically using AlphaEase FC v5.0.1 (Cell Biosciences, U.S.A.). The integrated density value (IDV) of the band from the gene of interest generated from the software was divided by the IDV from the band of the same sample but generated using the housekeeping gene.

Measuring Protein Abundance

Middle portion of the youngest fully expanded rice leaf grown in ambient or high CO₂ condition were collected between 0900 h and 1100 h and were used to measure GDCP protein abundance. Total soluble protein in the leaf was extracted by homogenizing leaf material in a pre-chilled mortar and pestle and the addition of a buffer (100 mM Bicine-KOH, pH 9.8 and 25 mM dithiothreitol). Proteins were separated on 10% SDS-PAGE with the protein concentration normalized based one leaf area of 1.98 mm². For some experiments, total leaf protein was measured using Bradford assay and normalized to sixmicrograms for Western blotting. The resulting gel was electroblotted onto a polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) membrane and probed with antisera against GDCP protein (provided by Asaph Cousins, Washington State University, USA). The

antibody can detect the presence of the two GDCP isoforms found in rice. A secondary antibody conjugated with peroxidase was used to produce chemiluminescent bands using ECL Western Blotting Detection Reagents (GE Healthcare, UK). The band with correct size corresponding to the protein of interest was analyzed using AlphaEase FC as described above. Based on the same blot image, the relative protein knockdown is measured by dividing the protein IDV of transgenic sample with the protein IDV of the wild type or tissue cultured control sample.

Soluble Amino Acid Analysis

The difference in total amino acid content between samples was analyzed using High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). Youngest fully expanded leaves were harvested using a steel clamp pre-cooled in liquid nitrogen. Leaf materials were freeze dried for three days and shipped to University of Sheffield (Department of Animal and Plant Sciences, Mass Spectrometry Facility, Sheffield, UK) for the HPLC analysis.

Freeze dried leaf samples were ground into powder with the aid of liquid N and weighed to approximately 100 mg. Seven hundred fifty (750) μL pre-chilled extraction buffer (80 μL water, 200 μL chloroform, 470 μL methanol) was added to each sample. Samples were homogenized by vortexing and left on ice for 30 min. Four hundred (400) μL sterile water was added per sample, vortexed, and centrifuged at 14000 rpm for two min until the layers separated. The aqueous layer was transferred into a new tube and the

chloroform layer was added with 400 μ L sterile water and the process was repeated. The two aqueous layer were combined and stored at -80°C

The amino acid content was analyzed through High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) using the pre-column ortho-phthaldialdehyde (OPA) derivatisation and fluorescence detection. Primary amine functional groups react with OPA to produce fluorescent OPA-amino acid compound. The OPA derivatised sample solution in borate buffer were separated using Phenomenex (Macclesfield, UK) LUNA C₈ (250 x 4.6mm). The analytes have excitation wavelength at 340 nm and emission wavelength at 455 nm.

Carbohydrate Analysis

Carbohydrate amounts in the leaf were analyzed and sampled the same way as mentioned above. Freeze-clamped samples were immediately placed in liquid-N during sampling and stored at -80°C freezer. Frozen leaf tissues were finely ground using pre-chilled mortar and pestle and placed into screw cap tubes containing 100 mg per sample. Ice-cold 0.7M perchloric acid was used to extract the soluble sugars by adding 1mL to each tube. After mixing and centrifugation (21,100 xg), soluble fraction was transferred into new tube for soluble sugar analysis while the remaining supernatant was washed, at least four times, with 80% ethanol, air dried and resuspended in water. The starch in the insoluble fraction was gelatinized by boiling for four hours and was hydrolyzed overnight by adding one unit of amyloglucosidase and 10 units of α -amylase and incubation at

37°C. The starch content was measured enzymatically using spectrophotometer as the function of the glucose units in the hydrolyzed sample as described by Smith and Zeeman (2006). The soluble fraction was neutralized to pH 6 by adding 2 M KOH, 0.4 M KCL, which produced potassium perchlorate precipitate after centrifugation (21,100 xg) for 10 min at 4°C. The total volume of the final neutralized solution was measured and an aliquot of the solution was used for enzymatic determination of sucrose, fructose, and glucose (Smith and Zeeman, 2006). This assay measures absorbance of the solution at 340 nm which comes from the reduction of NAD to NADH through the action of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase on the glucose-6-phosphate produced through the enzymatic conversions of starch, sucrose, fructose, and glucose.

Photosynthetic Measurements

Transgenic plants that showed significant reduction in the expression of the P-protein were subjected to leaf gas-exchange measurement to determine its effect on photosynthesis. Plants analyzed were either grown in ambient air or inside a high CO₂ chamber (10,000 ppm). All measurements were carried between 0800 h and 1300 h in a room with temperature of approximately 30°C. Middle portion of the youngest fully expanded leaves at mid-tillering were examined using a LI-6400XT portable photosynthesis system (LICOR Biosciences, Lincoln, NE, USA) to obtain the response of photosynthesis in varying C_i (intercellular CO₂) (A-C_i curve) and in varying light intensity (light response curve, LRC). The measurements were taken at constant airflow rate of 400 μmol s⁻¹, leaf temperature of 30 °C and a leaf-to-air vapor pressure deficit of

between 1.0 and 1.5 kPa. The oxygen concentration in the cuvette (2% or 21%) was controlled to examine the effects of low photorespiratory condition.

The A-Ci curve was determined by increasing C_a (ambient CO₂ concentration) from 20 to 2,000 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at a photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) of 2,000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Varying C_a would elicit changing intercellular CO₂ concentration (C_i , $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and hence changing net rate of CO₂ assimilation (A , $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). The initial linear points of the A-Ci curve was used to obtain the carboxylation efficiency (CE, $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) from its slope, and CO₂ compensation point (Γ , $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) from its x-intercept. The maximum photosynthetic rate (P_{max} , $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) was obtained from the highest A value from the curve.

The light response curve was obtained by decreasing PPFD from 2,000 to 20 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at a C_a of 400 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The initial linear points of the curve were used to determine quantum efficiency (Φ , $\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ photons}$) from its slope. The maximum rate of electron transport (J_{max}) was obtained from the highest A value from the curve.

The dark respiration rate (R_d) and maximum PSII quantum efficiency (F_v/F_m) was measured using a portable fluorometer (PAM 2500, Walz, Effeltrich, Germany) and PamWin-3 software (Walz, Effeltrich, Germany). The F_v/F_m was calculated as ($F_m -$

$F_o)/F_m$ on leaves dark adapted for 20 min using a Walz DLC-08 leaf clip (Genty, Briantais, & Baker, 1989).

Dark respiration rate (R_d) measurements were made between 0800 h and 1300 h on the mid-portion of the leaf blade of a mid-tillering stage plant grown in high (10,000 ppm) CO₂ conditions. Leaf blades were dark adapted for 20 min at a C_a of 400 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was done using STAR Software (Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research, Version: 2.0.1, IRRI, 2013). Graphs were generated using Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corp, U.S.A.). Most of the statistical analyses were performed using one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) in complete randomized design (CRD) provided that the assumptions were satisfied using the test for homogeneity of variance (Bartlett's) and test for normality of the residuals (Shapiro-Wilk). Least Significant Difference (LSD) test was used as post-hoc analysis by pairwise comparison of group means after significant difference was observed in ANOVA. For some of the parameters measured that does not satisfy the assumption of ANOVA due the nature of the raw values (i.e. a lot of zero values), the equivalent non-parametric test for one-way ANOVA, which is Kruskal Wallis H test on ranks, was used. The Dunn's test was used as post-hoc analysis by pairwise comparison of ranks. For all of the test statistics, p value was always set to 0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Generation and Transformation of amiGDCP Constructs

amiGDCP Construct Design

Artificial microRNA that would target GDCP genes in rice (amiGDCP) was designed using WMD3 tools (<http://wmd3.weigelworld.org/cgi-bin/webapp.cgi>) as described in Warthmann et al. (2013). The two GDCP genes in rice: Os01g51410 (GDCP1, 2 splice forms) and Os06g40940 (GDCP2, 3 splice forms) were used to design the amiRNA. As discussed by Warthmann et al. (2013), the predictive nature of the amiRNA design entails a strategy to create two different amiRNA constructs per experiment to ensure increase in likelihood of achieving good knockdown using amiRNA technology. The top two sequences generated by the web tool that do not have predicted off target gene effects (based from the *Oryza sativa* cDNA v5, TIGR database target search) were selected.

The first amiRNA target has the sequence 5'-CTGTGATGCTCTAATCTCAAT at genomic positions +2910 to +2930 of GDCP1 and +2947 to +2967 of GDCP2 with respect to their longest splice variants. The sequence is conserved across the different splice variants since it lies in an exonic region specifically near the 3' end of the coding region. The amiRNA sequence has hybridization energy of 36.05kcal/mol (87.29 %

sequence similarity with the target) with its target sequence. This amiRNA sequence once placed in the osa-MIR528 backbone is referred to as amiGDCP.1.

The second amiRNA target has the sequence 5'-TAGCTTTATTGACTAGCATTG at positions +3411 to +3431 bp of GDCP1 and +3446 to +3466 bp of GDCP2 with respect to their longest splice variants. The sequence is conserved across the different splice variants since it lies in an exonic region within the 3'untranslated region (3'UTR). The amiRNA sequence has hybridization energy of -35.37kcal/mol (91.02 % sequence similarity with the target) with its target sequence. This amiRNA sequence once placed in the osa-MIR528 backbone is referred to as amiGDCP.2.

osa-MIR528 is a naturally occurring rice microRNA that was previously used as a backbone to silence rice gene of interest with good efficiency (Lin et al., 2016; Warthmann et al., 2008). The two 21 base pair sequence (miRNA and miRNA*) of osa-MIR528 was replaced with the new amiRNA sequence that would target the GDCP genes. The resulting gene cassette was driven by the maize PEPC promoter and NOS terminator to limit the expression of the amiGDCP in rice mesophyll cells.

In this study, the longer ~1300bp 5'-flanking region of ZmPEPC (-1212 to +78) was used as a promoter, which showed mesophyll specific expression in rice (Lin et al., 2016; Matsuoka et al., 1994). The maize PEPC 0.6 kb promoter was previously characterized to drive preferential GUS expression in rice mesophyll cells of its leaf

blade and sheath tissue (Matsuoka et., 1994; Taniguchi et al., 2000; Kausch et. al., 2001; Tolley et. al., 2012).

Generation of amiGDCP constructs

After the selection of amiRNA sequence that targets rice GDCP genes, the WMD3 web tool also generated appropriate primers for given miRNA backbone which, the amiRNA will be placed. Table 1 shows the four primers for each construct (amiGDCP.1 and amiGDCP.2) to be used for incorporating the amiRNA sequences. Three separate PCR reactions were done to introduce the new amiRNA and amiRNA* sequences to the osa-MIR528 backbone in IRS499. The fourth PCR reaction is the fusion PCR where the three products from the previous PCRs were used as a template to be fused together using universal outside primers (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. The three PCR reactions (A, B, C) done to replace the amiRNA/amiRNA* sequence of IRS499 (A.). A fourth PCR reaction (D) was done to fuse the three PCR products from previous reactions (B.).

The product of fourth PCR reaction and the IRS499 plasmid were double digested with *Bst*EII and *Hind*III-HF (Fig. 12). The 734 bp fragment of the digested PCR product served as the insert while the 7560 bp fragment of the digested IRS499 plasmid served as the backbone. Since *Bst*EII and *Hind*III-HF have different restriction sites and produce different sticky ends, this would ensure the proper orientation of the insert to the backbone when mixed and ligated with T4 DNA Ligase.

Figure 12. PCR products from were double digested with *Bst*EII and *Hind*III-HF showing expected band sizes. The IRS499 template plasmid was also digested with the same enzymes to produce complementary sticky ends for the digested PCR products.

After the ligation reaction, the ligated products were transformed into competent *E. coli* cells using heat-shock method. The resistant colonies after transformation was PCR verified and plasmids of the PCR positive colonies were isolated. The size of the plasmids were verified by digestion with *Kpn*I that should produce 7062 bp and 1565 bp. *Kpn*I was an ideal enzyme to use since it cuts the plasmid at the start of the promoter and downstream the amiRNA gene that gives a short fragment of 1565 bp which when verified would indicate that the insert was ligated properly to the backbone. Figure 13A

shows the colony PCR of three PCR positive colonies per construct and showing expected restriction fragments after *KpnI* digestion. These six colonies were sent for sequencing for verification.

Figure 13. Colony PCR using amiRNA-F and amiRNA-R primers of kanamycin resistant colonies from the amiGDCP.1 and amiGDCP.2 bacterial transformations (A). Digestion of the PCR positive colonies with *KpnI* to verify the size of the plasmid with inserts (B.). C1-C3 refers to the colony names.

From the three colonies per construct that was sent for sequencing, one colony per construct with the correct expected sequence were chosen and transformed into *Agrobacterium*. After transformation into *Agrobacterium*, kanamycin resistant colonies

were again PCR verified and subjected to restriction digestion with *Kpn*I (Fig. 13B). The final *Agrobacterium* colonies which passed all the verification steps were given IRS numbers which were IRS896 for the amiGDCP.1 and IRS897 for the amiGDCP.2 which also serves as the plant ID of the transformed plants.

Figure 14. PCR of *Agrobacterium* colonies bearing amiGDCP.1 and amiDDCP.2, using the plasmid from the *E. coli* clones as positive control (A.). Restriction digestion of the plasmid isolated from the PCR positive *Agrobacterium* colonies exhibiting expected band sizes (B.).

Agrobacterium bearing amiGDCP.1 (IRS896) and amiGDCP.2 (IRS897) constructs were used for rice transformation. Since both constructs do not contain hygromycin resistance gene which is necessary for the selection in plant transformation, another construct bearing just the hygromycin gene (IRS485) was co-transformed with each amiRNA gene. In total, there were two rice transformation setups namely; IRS896/485 and IRS897/485. Co-transformation would affect the efficiency of the transformation (with respect to the amiGDCP constructs) since some plantlets that would

regenerate after a series of selection might be only positive for the hygromycin construct but absent with the amiGDCP construct. An advantage of this approach is that there is a chance that hygromycin gene would segregate independently of the amiGDCP gene, because the two T-DNA can independently integrate in the genome (Gelvin, 2003). The possibility of segregating out the hygromycin resistance gene through selection across generation would eliminate any unwanted phenotypic effects associated with having the hygromycin resistance gene.

Plant transformation was performed on 100 immature rice (IR64 variety) embryos using *Agrobacterium* mediated plant transformation at the Genetic Transformation Laboratory, IRRI. Wild-type rice immature embryos were also cultured on media without hygromycin to serve as tissue culture control to account for soma-clonal variation induced by hormones in tissue culture process.

Molecular Verification of GDCP Knockdown in T₀ Plants

PCR Screening of T₀ Plants

A total of seven calli were regenerated for IRS896 and 17 for IRS897. To somehow increase the number of plants, calli were regenerated into more than one plantlet were separated but was still noted as sister plants because they came from the same resistant callus (denoted by A, B, C... after their event number). Primers specific to the amiRNA were used as the reverse primer while a compatible forward primer was

designed from the maize PEPC promoter since both sequence is not present in wild type rice genome (Table 1).

Out of the seven plantlets regenerated from IRS896 transformation only two events were positive for the *amiGDCP.1* construct (Fig. 15). Only IR64-IRS896/485-1 and IR64-IRS896/485-3 were PCR positive, while IR64-IRS896/485-2 showed one PCR positive plant but upon two repeat PCR reactions it was proven to be PCR negative. Seven plants were PCR positive out of 17 plants for IRS897 (Fig. 16). These events were from IR64-IRS897/485-1 to -7. PCR negative plants were all discarded.

Plants were transferred into hydroponic trays with Yoshida Culture Solution (YCS) prior to transplanting into pots. After three days in hydroponics, the leaves of plants were noticeably pale, this was most apparent in the IRS896 PCR positive plants. Plants were transferred into a high CO₂ chamber (5000 ppm CO₂). The recovery of the plant leaves when transferred into high CO₂ chamber was the first indication that there could be impairment in the photorespiratory pathway (Somerville & Ogren, 1982). After two weeks in hydroponics the plants were transferred into 0.5L pots at high CO₂ chamber. After another two weeks in small pots they were transferred into 7L pots and returned to ambient CO₂ condition. All the plants from IRS896 and, events 2 and 6 from IRS897 showed response when grown for three days in ambient air, hence were grown inside the high CO₂ chamber until maturity while the other plants were grown in ambient air condition. Figure 17 shows the different phenotypes of the T₀ lines from IRS896 and IRS897 at flowering stage.

Figure 15. Agarose gel image of IRS896 T₀ PCR screening. Plants that contain the amiGDCP.1 construct produced PCR product of 417 bp. The IRS896 plasmid was used as positive control while water and rice tissue culture control were used as negative controls.

Figure 16. Agarose gel image of IRS897 T₀ PCR screening. Plants that contain the amiGDCP.2 construct produced PCR product of 393 bp. The IRS897 plasmid was used as positive control while water and rice tissue culture control were used as negative controls.

Figure 17. Representative images of T₀ PCR positive plants. Tissue culture control (A.); IRS896 carrying amiGDPC.1 (B); and IRS897 carrying amiGDPC.2 (C).

Southern Blot Analysis

Gene copy number analysis is an important technique in transgenic work to identify the number of times the T-DNA harboring the gene of interest was inserted to the genome, as this might help in interpreting the phenotypes observed (Gelvin, 2003). T-DNA gets integrated in the rice genome in random fashion; hence the number of T-DNA copies integrated in the genome is equivalent to the number of potential insertional mutations that occurred. In practice, single copy events are favored for analysis to minimize the potential effects of insertional mutants.

Southern blot was used to analyze the copy number of IRS896 and IRS897, as well as the co-transformed IRS485. The few number of plants generated from the plant

transformation could be attributed to the co-transformation of the selectable marker. There could have been more calli which contained the amiRNA gene but these might have not had the hygromycin resistance gene and have died in the selection process in tissue culture. Or there could be some regenerated plants which survived because they contain the hygromycin resistance gene but do not contain the amiRNA gene.

Figure 18 shows the southern blot of IRS896 and IRS897 probed with ZmUbiquitin promoter specific probe. Most of the events are highly multi-copy with IRS896-3 having the lowest copy number of 3. Two enzymes were used to separate the genomic DNA in order to validate correct copy number. The same blots were used to re-probe with the hygromycin resistance gene specific probe. Table 2 shows the summary of the copy number for both the amiRNA genes and the hygromycin resistance gene. It is worth noting that some events have numerous copy numbers that even using other restriction enzyme was not possible to discern the correct copy numbers. The amiRNA gene copy number for the two constructs ranges from 3-16 copies, while the hygromycin resistance gene had at least one copy which is sufficient enough to provide resistance from the selection process. The southern blot data of sister plants of each event were performed is not shown here. Sister plants of each event share the same copy number genotype, proving that they were clones of each other.

Multiple copy number usually produce reduction in gene expression of transgenes through several pathway of transcriptional or post-transcriptional regulation (Li et al., 2002). Transcriptional regulation could have come from DNA-methylation or co-

suppression due to several copies of the same promoter (Rajeevkumar et al., 2015). Based on experience working on transgenic rice, it is a rare occasion to produce few successful transformants which is primarily multi-copy, especially starting from 100 immature rice embryos. Having only multiple copy gene insertion in *Agrobacterium* mediated transformation is not common (M. Cheng et al., 1997). Unless there is a selective pressure that allowed the regeneration of only multiple gene copy like in this case the selectable marker is on a different plasmid and co-transformed with the gene of interest. The number of copies observed in the southern blot does not equate to the same number of genome insertion. Genes to be inserted by the *Agrobacterium* is flanked by the T-DNA border are sometimes inserted in a concatenated manner producing differently sized bands which can be bigger than expected (Jones, et al., 1987; Jorgensen, et al., 1987). The bands of a multi-copy in Southern blot that does not segregate in future or linked could be concatemers from in the same insertion site (De Block & Debrouwer, 1991). Though it is difficult to accurately determine the gene copy of transgenic plants, Southern blots provides at least a close approximate (Kohli, et al., 2010).

The multi-copy nature of the produced transformants could have implied that single copy events might have been selected against. Since the constructs transformed functions as artificial gene silencing it can be hypothesized that fewer copy events might have induced stronger knockdown. And multi-copy events had some level of transcriptional or post-transcriptional silencing of the amiGDGP constructs (Gelvin, et al., 1983; Hepburn, et al., 1983; Luo & Chen, 2007). The hypothesis can be verified by

tracking the segregation of gene copy number of the multi-copy transgenic plants as it advance through generation.

The preliminary analysis of the phenotype of the T₀ generation appears to be analogous among the few plants that represent each construct, and the difference in copy number do not seem to have a large effect on the variation of response between plants of the same construct.

Table 2. Summary of amiRNA gene and hygromycin resistance gene copy numbers of the rice transgenic plants produced.

Transgenic Event	No. of amiRNA Gene Copy	No. of Hygromycin Resistance Gene Copy
IR64-IRS896/485-1	>11	7
IR64-IRS896/485-3	3	2
IR64-IRS897/485-1	>13	2
IR64-IRS897/485-2	5	1
IR64-IRS897/485-3	>11	6
IR64-IRS897/485-4	>10	4
IR64-IRS897/485-5	>13	5
IR64-IRS897/485-6	>16	4
IR64-IRS897/485-7	6	1

Figure 18. Southern blot images of IRS896 and IRS897 T₀ plants. Genomic DNA samples were digested with either *HindIII* or *AflII* restriction enzymes. Blots were hybridized using ZmPEPC promoter specific probe to analyze the number of amiRNA gene insertions as well as hygromycin resistance gene specific probe for the plant selectable marker. RC is the wildtype rice control as a negative control. P is the plasmid of the construct being analyzed that serve as the positive control.

Transcript Expression Analysis

Artificial microRNA acts at the post-transcriptional level where in plants would lead to transcript cleavage thereby lowering the transcript residency of the gene of

interest (Ossowski et al., 2008; Warthmann et al., 2013). Hence, sqRT-PCR was used to examine the transcript abundance of the GDCP genes in rice to determine if the amiGDCP gene works in reducing the GDCP gene transcripts in the transgenic lines.

sqRT-PCR data shows that the GDCP transcript were also reduced in the T₀ plants (Figs. 19 and 20). This evidence supports that the reductions observed in the GDCP protein levels of transgenic plants was due to the amiRNA transgene that directs the cleavage of the GDCP transcripts in rice.

Figure 19. sqRT-PCR of glycine decarboxylase complex P protein (GDCP) gene expression in T₀ GDCP knockdown lines. Gel image of GDCP sqRT-PCR (33 cycles) using primers that amplify either of the two GDCP genes in rice (A), gel image of GAPDH sqRT-PCR used as housekeeping gene to normalize the GDCP expression (B), and gel image of RNA quality samples used in the experiment.

Figure 20. Relative glycine decarboxylase complex P protein (GDCP) gene expression from sqRT-PCR, normalized against rice tissue culture control (100%). T₀ plants showed similar reductions in the GDCP transcript with the GDCP protein with IRS896 plants showing the greatest reduction in transcript of up to 80%. Standard error represents the technical replicates.

As seen on Figure 20, IRS896 had better effect in knocking down GDCP genes than IRS897. The efficiency of the amiRNA constructs to guide the natural RNA silencing complex (RISC) to target desired genes relies on the (1) location of the 20bp amiRNA and its target region and (2) the strength of the promoter driving the expression of the amiRNA construct (Guleria et al., 2011; Warthmann et al., 2008). The location of the amiRNA that would give the best knockdown would be hard to predict but analysis of the naturally occurring microRNAs in rice helped scientist to make a predictive online tool to assess the on-target or off-target efficiency of an amiRNA silencing, but it does not guarantee knockdown until tested (Wang et al., 2010). Once the 20bp amiRNA guided the RISC to cut the gene of interest (GOI), the amiRNA will also be cut as consequence; hence if the expression of amiRNA gene is not high enough to complement the GOI, it will result to protein expression of the uncut GOI transcripts.

Since both constructs share the same promoter, the location of the amiRNA target could affect the knockdown efficiency between the constructs. The location of the IRS896 amiRNA target lies on the 3' end of the coding region while the IRS897 target lies in the 3' untranslated region. Based on the results, targeting the 3' end of the coding region appears to induce better knockdown than targeting the 3' untranslated region. The ZmPEPC promoter has a strong enough expression to induce strong reduction in both GDCP isoform gene expressions.

Western Blot Screening

PCR positive plants were subjected to western blot screening using antibody raised against pea (*Pisum sativum*) GDCP protein to see if the GDCP protein expression was knocked down (Fig. 21). The antibody was tested prior to the experiment and was found to detect the rice GDCP protein with the predicted size of ~100 kDa (monomer) but the antibody had also unspecific binding with smaller unknown proteins with one probably Rubisco large subunit because of the relative size of the band. Since the unspecific binding does overlap with the GDCP protein, it could still be used to measure the GDCP protein expression in western blot.

Densitometric analysis of the GDCP bands indicate that the two events of IRS 896 had undetectable levels of GDCP protein while IRS897 had varying protein reduction across the seven events with up to 80% reduction (Fig. 22). The results show a very high reduction in GDCP protein expression compared to wild type, especially the

plants from IRS896 which might explain the differences observed in their response to ambient air. The reduction in protein expression could explain why some transgenic plants exhibit classical photorespiratory impaired phenotype when grown in ambient air. The classical photorespiratory impaired mutant screening was done in the past by exposing mutant populations into ambient air condition to select plants that would have leaf chlorosis or stunted growth but would recover when transferred into CO₂ enriched environment (Blackwell et al., 1988; Somerville et. al., 1982).

GDCP silencing in tobacco using anti-sense RNA interference driven by ST-LS1 (from a photosystem II protein) promoter showed only 60-70% reduction in GDCP protein (Heineke et al., 2001). All the tobacco GDCP knockdown plants were viable under ambient air though had reduced growth rates, similar to most of the IRS897 plants which did not have greater a than 50% reduction in GDCP expression. The result implies severe reduction of GDCP is needed to observe photorespiratory impaired phenotype and altered C₂ cycle response in photosynthetic measurements.

Figure 21. T₀ western blot of PCR positive plants of IRS896 and IRS897 showing reduce GDCP protein against the tissue culture controls. The rice GDCP protein is shown at ~100 kDa molecular weight mark. There were unspecific binding to two other smaller proteins but the GDCP band is still clear for densitometric analysis. Corresponding Coomassie-stained parallel gel is indicated to show equal protein loading rates.

Figure 22. Relative GDCP protein expression normalized against the rice control (100%) in the same blot. T₀ plants showed varying reduction in GDCP protein with greatest reduction in IRS896 while some events in IRS897 had equal protein amounts relative to the rice control. No biological replicates.

Gas exchange measurements

Photosynthetic measurements were performed to assess effect of knocking down GDCP expression in the leaves on photosynthesis. As well as to compare the observed phenotype with the classical photorespiratory impaired phenotype found in knockdown mutants (Timm and Bauwe, 2013). Since the plants were still in T₀ generation and in which effect of somaclonal variation is highest due to tissue culture, analysis was performed along with a germinated wildtype a part from the tissue culture control. Tissue culture control is the same IR64 rice that underwent the tissue culture process but was not transformed by *Agrobacterium*. The extent of the photosynthetic measurements done was also limited since each event is treated as an individual treatment and in T₀ biological replicates is not possible. The T₀ photosynthetic measurement serves as preliminary analysis of the GDCP knockdown lines.

Full net CO₂ assimilation rate against changing intercellular CO₂ concentration (A-Ci curve) and light response curve (LRC) was performed for the only two events in IRS896 (event 1 and 3), while four events were selected for IRS897 (events 1, 3, 4, and 7), shown in Figures 23 and 24, respectively. All the photosynthetic parameters observed in the tissue culture control plant were significantly different from the true wild type values (Fig. 23). These differences could be attributed to large effect of soma-clonal variation in T₀ plants induced by the previous tissue culture propagation (Morrison, et al., 1988).

IRS896 plants had the most severe response in ambient air which explains the stark reduction in all the photosynthetic parameters tested. For instance, the P_{max} or maximum photosynthetic rate at saturating intercellular CO_2 was reduced in the two representative events by as much as 90% compared to the wildtype. Compensation points (x-intercept of A-Ci curve) were six times higher than that of wild type (Fig. 23B). The photosynthetic rate at 400 ppm C_a (atmospheric CO_2 concentration) was reduced to about 0.5 to 0.9 $\text{mmol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ compared to 28 $\text{mmol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in wildtype, which indicates that it is barely performing photosynthesis in ambient air. This was associated with very low stomatal conductance of the events 1 and 3 which were around 0.05 to 0.1 $\text{mmol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ compared to 0.65 to 0.70 $\text{mmol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in true wildtype plants. Studies have shown that photorespiration can control stomatal regulation and hence control intercellular CO_2 and O_2 (Eisenhut et al., 2016; Igamberdiev et al., 2004). The low photosynthetic rates even in saturating ambient CO_2 concentration can be explain by the very low stomatal conductance. All measurements (A-Ci curve and LRC) were made at ambient O_2 concentration of 21%. O_2 is the primary substrate of Rubisco that induces photorespiration. The very low stomatal conductance of GDCP knockdown lines at C_a of 400 ppm (0.04%) indicates that the rate of photorespiration in this condition promotes the closure of stomata to prevent further photorespiration, hence the observed low photosynthetic rates. The appreciable increase in photosynthetic rate in the knockdown lines at C_a of 2000 ppm indicates the higher CO_2 slightly reduce the rate of photorespiration but still not comparable to the wildtype response (Fig. 23). The high compensation point could also indicate altered photorespiration since it can be defined as the point where CO_2 assimilation due to photosynthesis is equal to CO_2 release from

apparent respiration in the light. Apparent respiration is the sum of mitochondrial respiration and photorespiratory release of CO₂ that both occurred in the presence of light (Meidner, 1970). The impaired CO₂ assimilation is clearly observed in the GDCP knockdown plants but further detailed analysis is needed to prove that this is due to altered C₂ cycle.

On the other hand the LRC (Fig. 23C and D) show that photosynthesis of the GDCP knockdown saturates at light intensity of around 400 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ with a maximum rate of electron transport (J_{max}) at 1.4 $\mu\text{mol e}^{-} \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, compared to wildtype that has not yet saturated even at 2000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and J_{max} of 21.5 and 32.3 for tissue culture control and true wildtype respectively. It has been proven that photorespiration acts as energy sink in excess light where the chloroplasts produce excess reducing power and ATP (Igamberdiev, et al., 2001). The consumption of reducing power and ATP by photorespiration helps prevent photoinhibition (Wingler, et al., 2000). The over reduction of chloroplast due to impaired photorespiration in the GDCP knockdown lines causes the inhibition of repair of photodamaged photosystem II leading to photoinhibition observed in Figure 23C and D (Takahashi & Badger, 2011).

Figure 23. A-Ci curves (A and B) and light response curve (C and D) of the IRS896 T₀ plants. A-Ci curves show the rate of CO₂ assimilation as a function of intercellular CO₂ concentration. LRC show the rate of CO₂ assimilation as a function of irradiance. IRS896 plants show dramatic decrease in the rate of CO₂ assimilation across a broad range of intercellular CO₂ concentration at saturating light intensity. The B and D figures are a magnified image of figures A and C to observe clearly the values of CO₂ assimilation rates at low intercellular CO₂ concentration and low irradiance levels, respectively. For A-Ci curve measurements were made at light intensity of 2,000 μmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹ and a leaf temperature of 30°C. While for the LRC, measurements were made at 400 ppm C_a and a leaf temperature of 30°C.

The seven events of IRS897 in general did not have severe response when grown in ambient compared to the two events of IRS896. The photosynthetic measurements of the four selected events showed no significant difference in all the parameters measured compared to tissue culture control (Fig. 24). Like the measurements made in IRS896, two to three healthy leaves were measured from selected plants to represent each of the events. Based from the result of the photosynthetic measurements, the selected plants for

each construct had similar trend that well represent the difference in observed phenotype between the two constructs.

Figure 24. ACi curves and light response curve (LRC) of the IRS897 T₀ plants. ACi curves show the rate of CO₂ assimilation as a function of intercellular CO₂ concentration. LRC show the rate of CO₂ assimilation as a function of irradiance. The B and D figures are a magnified image of figures A and C to observe clearly the values of CO₂ assimilation rates at low intercellular CO₂ concentration and low irradiance levels, respectively. For A-Ci curve measurements were made at light intensity of 2,000 μmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹ and a leaf temperature of 30°C. While for the LRC, measurements were made at 400 ppm C_a and a leaf temperature of 30°C.

Molecular Characterization of T₁ Plants

Germination of T₁ Generation

To have better and more accurate understanding of the effects of knocking down GDCP expression in rice mesophyll cells, IRS896 and IRS897 plants were advanced to T₁ generation. Apart from advancing the lines to check the stability of the phenotype across generation, each event from the two construct were germinated to select candidate lines for detailed analysis.

Table 3 contains the list of all the lines advanced to T₁ generation together with their corresponding copy number and germination efficiency. PCR screening summary was indicated. Ten seeds per line were germinated. Lines that produced very few T₁ seeds were germinated in MS media to increase the chance of germination. The germination efficiency was varied and ranges from 30-100%, and germination in media did not ensure 100% germination. All of the plants from both events from IRS896 showed the same photorespiratory impaired phenotype when grown in ambient air as observed previously in T₀ generation. Thus, they were grown in high CO₂ chamber (ICU, 10,000 ppm or 1% CO₂) until maturity.

Almost all germinated plants were PCR positive as expected since all of them were multi-copy events. Since sister plants of the same events were considered as clones based on their genotype copy number in T₀, it was decided to group the sister plants (i. e.

IRS896/485-3A, -3B, and -3C) as one event for the rest of the analysis to increase the number of biological replicates for some events (Table 3).

Table 3. List of T₀ lines advanced to T₁ generation. The T₀ generation gene copy number summary was indicated. The T₁ progenies were PCR screened for the amiRNA gene. Number of plants screened for GDCP protein expression using Western Blotting was also indicated.

Event/Line ID	No. of Gene Copies (T ₀)	Received	No. of seed germinated	Percent Germination	PCR positive	Grouping	Western Blot Screened
IR64-IRS896/485-1C	>11	10	10	100	10	896-1	10
IR64-IRS896/485-3A	3	10	5	50	5		
IR64-IRS896/485-3B	3	10	4	40	4	896-3	14
IR64-IRS896/485-3C	3	10	5	50	5		
IR64-IRS897/485-1A	>13	10	8	80	8		
IR64-IRS897/485-1B	>13	10	8	80	8	897-1	25
IR64-IRS897/485-1C	>13	10	9	90	9		
IR64-IRS897/485-2A	5	10	10	100	10	897-2	10
IR64-IRS897/485-3A	>11	10	6	60	6		
IR64-IRS897/485-3B	>11	10	7	70	7	897-3	19
IR64-IRS897/485-3C	>11	10	10	100	9		
IR64-IRS897/485-4A	>10	10	6	60	6		
IR64-IRS897/485-4B	>10	10	6	60	6	897-4	18
IR64-IRS897/485-4C	>10	10	8	80	8		
IR64-IRS897/485-5A	>13	10	4	40	4		
IR64-IRS897/485-5B	>13	10	9	90	9	897-5	8
IR64-IRS897/485-6A	>16	10	3	30	3	897-6	3
IR64-IRS897/485-7A	6	10	5	50	5		
IR64-IRS897/485-7B	6	10	7	70	7	897-7	15
IR64-IRS897/485-7C	6	10	7	70	7		
IR64-Tissue Culture Control	0	10	8	80	0	TCR	
IR64-A009-Wildtype	0	10	8	80	0	Wildtype	
				Total	136		122

Copy Number Analysis of T₁ Lines

Since all of the generated events for both IRS896 and IRS897 were multi copy, copy number analysis was performed again to determine the segregation pattern of the T₁ progenies. For the detailed analysis on the effect of GDCP knockdown on photosynthesis, fewer copies were favored to minimize the inherent effect of multiple insertion sites in the plant genome.

The two events of IRS 896 showed independent segregation of gene copies at T₁ generation as shown in Figure 26. IRS896-3 showed one of the three copies segregating and producing single copy event for IRS896. While IRS896-1, though still heavily multi-copy showed some bands disappearing, indicating not all copies are linked and segregation in future generation of a single copy is possible.

Figure 26. Southern blot images of IRS896 T₁ lines germinated for the selection of candidate events for detailed analysis. The maize ubiquitin promoter of the amiGDCP constructs was used as probe to minimize off target hybridization with the wildtype. MW is the DIG-labeled molecular weight marker that ranges from 23,130 bp to 2027 bp. RC is the wildtype rice control as a negative control. P is the plasmid of the construct being analyzed that serve as the positive control.

Figure 27. Southern blot images of IRS897 T₁ lines germinated for the selection of candidate events for detailed analysis. The maize ubiquitin promoter of the amiGDCP constructs was used as probe to minimize off target hybridization with the wildtype. MW is the DIG-labeled molecular weight marker that ranges from 23,130 bp to 2027 bp. RC is the wildtype rice control as a negative control. P is the plasmid of the construct being analyzed that serve as the positive control.

The seven events of IRS897 showed independent segregation of gene copies at T₁ generation as shown in Figure 27. IRS897-4 produced one single copy progeny out from 11 copies in T₀ generation. While IRS897-7 produced two single copy progeny out from five copies in T₀ generation. Only IRS 897-2 did not show segregation of its four gene copy, which could indicate strong linkage between the copies.

Western Blot Screening of T₁ Plants

Since single copy events were produced from both GDCP knockdown constructs at T₁ generation, it is interesting to see the effect in GDCP protein reduction between different numbers of gene copy from the two constructs. Western blotting was used to ultimately check the effectivity of the two construct in reducing the GDCP protein expression on the T₁ population.

Figure 28 shows the mean GDCP protein expression of the T₁ events of IRS896 and IRS897 from densitometric analysis of western blot bands. The two events from IRS896, events 1 and 3, showed significantly lower GDCP expression with almost undetectable values. Only event 2 from IRS897 showed significantly lower GDCP expression (about 60% reduction). The rest of the events in IRS897 had varying protein reduction with some events having more than the wildtype expression. The results show that the majority of the plants analyzed (10 out of 97 plants) from IRS897 had no significant difference with the wildtype regardless of copy number. It becomes more

apparent that the amiGDCP.2 target in the IRS897 construct does not induce good GDCP knockdown compared to IRS896, at least at the protein level.

Figure 28. Relative protein expression of T₁ lines from the two GDCP knockdown constructs. Protein expression is expressed in percentage relative to the wildtype (solid line, 100%) using densitometric analysis of western blot bands.

Correlation analysis between the amiRNA silencing gene copy and GDCP protein expression of both IRS896 and IRS897 T₁ lines is presented in Figure 29. The significantly reduced GDCP protein expression of the two events of IRS896 (Fig. 28) regardless of the difference in copy number already express the efficiency of the amiGDCP construct to induce silencing, at the protein level. Pearson correlation shows that there is a moderate positive linear relationship between the copy number and GDCP protein expression (Fig. 29A). Which means that IRS896-3 with 1-3 copy number have better GDCP protein reduction compared to IRS896-1 which has 6-11 copies. Lower gene knockdown on the plants that had multi copy gene inserts have been associated with

both transcriptional and post-transcriptional gene silencing which explains the observed higher GDCP expression in IRS897-1 (Kohli, et al., 2010).

On the other hand IRS897 T₁ lines had no significant linear relationship between copy number and GDCP protein expression (Fig. 29B). Similar variation observed in GDCP protein expression across increasing copy number indicates that regardless of copy number there is insufficient knockdown of GDCP, especially when compared to the reduction observed in IRS896 lines. The variation in the GDCP protein reduction in IRS897 cannot be explained by the presence of the amiGDCP.2 gene alone. These results indicate that the amiRNA gene designed for IRS897 do not provide sufficient and consistent knockdown of GDCP in rice leaves. For the detailed analysis on the effect of knocking down GDCP in rice leaves in photosynthesis, only the two events from IRS896 T₁ were considered.

Physiological Characterization of GDCP Knockdown in Rice

Physiological Effects of Growing in Different CO₂ Concentration

Events 1 and 3 of IRS896 showed severe photorespiratory impaired phenotype when grown in ambient air even in T₁ generation. Even when grown in ICU chamber (1% CO₂) the gross morphology of the plants is not similar to the wild type plants, though they manage to survive and produce seed (Fig. 30A). The knockdown plants had fewer tillers, stunted growth, and pale leaves, and when placed in ambient air condition, the leaves showed signs of bleaching, similar to classically described photorespiratory mutant phenotype (Timm and Bauwe, 2013).

To assess the effect of photorespiratory stress brought about by ambient air condition, the two candidate events of IRS896 were subjected to two CO₂ growing conditions, ICU (low photorespiratory stress, 1% CO₂) and ambient (high photorespiratory stress, 0.04% CO₂). Six randomly selected plants per event were used in the experiment as well as six wild type plants, thus 18 in total. Since the plants from the two events chosen were growing in ICU, the six wildtype plants were grown in the ICU as well. At mid-tillering stage, three of the IRS896-1, IRS896-3, and wildtype were transferred to ambient air condition (Fig. 30B) while the remaining half were left in the ICU (Fig.30A). At the eight day after transfer, two leaves per plant were tested for oxygen sensitivity using instantaneous gas exchange measurement. At the tenth day, one of the leaves used in the gas exchange measurement was sampled as the source of leaf

total RNA and protein, while the other leaf was sampled to measure leaf soluble amino acid and carbohydrate content.

Figure 30. Gross plant morphology of IRS896 T₁ generation selected lines. Each plant picture is a representative of three biological replicates. **(A)** Shows a set of plants that were kept in ICU for 10 days while **(B)** display an independent subset of plants that are moved out of ICU for 10 days in to ambient air condition. Clear changes in plant phenotype were observed in IRS896 plants exhibiting classical photorespiration impaired phenotype when exposed in ambient air.

The copy number of the six randomly selected lines from IRS896-1 and IRS896-3 is presented in Figure 31. Similar to the data presented earlier, the copy number of the selected T1 plants of IRS896-1 had 11-13 visible copies, while IRS896-3 had 2-3 copies of the amiRNA gene. The hygromycin copy numbers of IRS896-1 lines were all 6 copies, while the IRS896-3 had 1-2 copies. Since it was determined by the previous western blot data that the amiRNA gene copy number for IRS896 does not have a significant effect on gene knockdown efficiency within the events, it can be said that the population of the two events being studied would have similar GDCP knockdown efficiency.

Figure 31. Southern blot images of the selected IRS896 T₁ plants. (A) ZmPEPC specific probes were used to analyze the gene copy number of the amiGDCP constructs. (B) Shows the before blot gel image of the digested genomic DNA to show gel loading bias and DNA quality. (C) is the re-probed blot with hygromycin resistance gene specific probe.

Effects on GDCP Gene Expression

To see the response of the GDCP knockdown in different photorespiratory growing condition, selected plants GDCP protein expression were screened by western blotting. GDCH protein expression was also tested to identify if there was co-suppression of the other GDC subunit, brought about by the reduction in GDCP subunit (Oliver et al., 1990). Figure 32A and 32B show the representative blots for GDCP and GDCH, respectively. Both events of IRS896 showed undetectable level of GDCP expression and the different growing condition did not affect the protein reduction by the amiGDCP.

Clearly, the GDCP protein expression of the two IRS896 lines was significantly different to wild type plants. The difference in the GDCP protein expression corroborates with the severity of photorespiratory phenotype observed in different plant species with severe knockdown of C2 cycle genes (S. Timm & Bauwe, 2013). The GDCH expression of the GDCP knockdown lines on the other hand were not significantly different to the wildtype plants for those grown in ambient and even higher in some lines grown in ICU. This is congruent to a previous GDC knockdown studies which show that the GDCH expression is not affected by the GDCP expression but GDCP expression is affected by the suppression of GDCH (Blackwell et al., 1990; Heineke et al., 2001; Lin et al., 2016). Perhaps it indicates that GDCH as an amino-methyl carrier protein, has other functions in other important primary metabolism (Bauwe, 2011).

Figure 32. Western blot analyses of selected T_1 lines to quantify GDCP and GDCH protein expressions in knockdown lines. **(A)** Western blots and SDS-PAGE of knockdown lines showing great reduction in GDCP in IRS896 lines in both ICU and ambient grown plants. **(B)** GDCH protein expression was not significantly different to wildtype in GDCP knockdown lines.

The two GDCP isoform transcripts' expression was analyzed to prove that the reduction of the GDCP protein expression is because of the amiRNA gene and that it targets the two isoforms simultaneously. The effect of the two different growing CO₂ concentrations was also examined. RNA quality check and the primer melt curves used in qPCR are shown in Figure 35.

To check if both of the isoforms of GDCP were knocked down, isoform specific primers were used for qPCR (Table 1 and Fig. 38). Both isoforms were significantly reduced in the knockdown lines regardless of growing condition compared to wild type plant, proving that the observed reduction in the Western blots were due to post transcriptional silencing of both GDCP isoform transcripts.

A general trend of higher gene expression in the ambient compared to ICU grown plants was also observed (Fig. 33). Although the trend does not reflect the protein expression observed in different growing conditions. This might be due to the post transcriptional gene regulation nature of amiRNA gene. Unlike knockout mutants GDCP transcripts were still transcribe in the same manner as in the wildtype. However due to the presence of amiGDCP in the transgenic lines, the GDCP transcript are cleaved after transcription and will be prone to endogenous RNAses which will degrade the transcripts (X. Wang et al., 2010). The cleaved transcripts might still be present in the cell but will not be functional for translation to happen (Dugas & Bartel, 2004). These remaining unviable transcripts can still be picked up by the qPCR technique due to its sensitivity. The slight increase in the expression of GDCP isoforms at ambient conditions could be

due to inherent positive feedback to increase their transcription in high photorespiratory stress condition. Though the precise regulatory signal transduction pathway that induces increase in GDCP expression might not be well elucidated, but it has been established that the expression of C₂ cycle genes are upregulated in drought condition which has similar characteristics to photorespiratory stress (Wingler et al., 1999).

Figure 33. qPCR analysis of the two GDCP transcript expression in knockdown lines using GDCP isoform specific primers.

To verify the results of the relationship of protein expression between GDCP and GDCH, qPCR was performed using GDCP specific primer (regardless of isoform) and GDCH (Os10g0516100, isoform highly expressed in the leaf) specific primers. As expected, the GDCP transcript expression was significantly reduced in the transgenic lines, verifying the previous qPCR results. The GDCH transcript expression however showed significantly lower expression in the IRS896 lines which do not reflect the observed protein expression. One possible reason could be due to the rate of protein turnover of GDCH proteins in the transgenic lines, which could be slower in the GDCP knockdown lines. For the GDCH transcript expression there was no significant difference in expression at different growing condition.

Figure 34. qPCR analysis of GDCP and GDCH transcript expression in the knockdown lines using non-isoform specific primers.

Figure 35. RNA quality check of samples used for gene expression analysis. **(A)** RNA samples run in 2% agarose gel showing good quality exhibited by the distinct types of RNA. **(B)** the log transformed melt curve for the primers for Figure 33. **(C)** the log transformed melt curve for the primers for Figure 34. Both log transformed melt curves show single peaks.

Effects on Soluble Amino Acid and Carbohydrates

The best evidence that can connect the direct effect of the GDCP knockdown and impairment of photorespiration is the accumulation of the substrate of GDCP which is glycine. Glycine accumulation in the leaf during the day is primarily attributed to the C₂ cycle activity (Oliver, 1994). Previously discovered mutants lacking GDC activity exhibit significant increase in accumulation of glycine with respect to a significant increase in glycine/serine ratio compared to wildtype during the day (Blackwell et al., 1990; Novitskaya, et al., 2002).

Figure 36 clearly shows the significant increase in glycine and glycine/serine ratio thus confirming the GDCP knockdown or GDC impairment in the transgenic lines grown in different CO₂ concentration. While, serine values of the transgenic lines were not significantly different from the wildtype. The response of the glycine and serine in the knockdown lines was also observed in the GDCH knockdown in rice (Lin et al., 2016). Though amount of the accumulated glycine was much higher in the GDCP knockdown lines, it could be attributed to the less severe photorepiratory phenotype of the GDCH knockdown lines due to the expression of other GDCH isoforms that could complement the knockdown. Serine levels observed in the GDCH knockdown in rice were also not significantly different from the wildtype during the measurements done in the day but significantly different during the night, which indicates residual GDC activity and mild photorespiratory phenotype (Lin et al., 2016). Though serine is primarily synthesized by the C₂ cycle in photosynthetically active cells during the day, there are still other

biosynthetic pathways that can produce serine which could explain the unperturbed serine values in the GDC knockdown lines (Ros et al., 2013)(Ros et. al., 2014). Serine is also a known metabolite signal in plants that positively regulates the transcription of C₂ cycle genes (D. J. Oliver & Sarojini, 1987; S. Timm et al., 2013). The sustained serine amounts in the leaves of GDC knockdown plants via alternative biosynthetic pathways ensure the constitutive expression of C₂ cycle genes especially in high photorespiratory conditions.

Figure 36. Leaf soluble glycine and serine content of IRS896 lines subjected to high CO₂ (ICU) and ambient air conditions. **(A)** Glycine contents of the IRS896 lines showed greatest increase compared to wild type plants which is almost near the limit of detection. **(B)** Serine content of the IRS896 lines showed similar values **(C)** Glycine serine ratios of all the lines were significantly higher compared to wild type.

High accumulation of glycine and serine in the ambient condition compared to ICU indicates direct response of the glycine accumulation with respect to higher photorespiratory stress brought by environmental condition. The very high glycine concentration of the knockdown plants reached about 260 times of the wildtype in ambient. The accumulation indicates that the GDC contributes to the majority of glycine metabolism in photosynthetically active tissues (Neuburger et al., 1986). The significant loss of GDCP in the knockdown plants shows its effects to the overall GDC activity leading to the high accumulation of glycine.

The results are partly expected since rice has a lot more photosynthetically active mesophyll cells compared to bundle sheath cells that can perform photorespiration (T. L. Sage & Sage, 2009). In one part, high glycine accumulation in the mesophyll cells through the knockdown of GDC is desired to produce a gradient that drive its transport into the bundle sheath cells, similar to what is observed in C_3 - C_4 intermediate plants (Schulze et al., 2016). But the desired decarboxylation of glycine in the bundle sheath cells to drive the CO_2 concentrating mechanism of C_2 photosynthesis does not appear to happen, due to observed glycine accumulation.

The first possible reason is that there are not enough photosynthetically active bundle sheath cells that can support the amount of glycine produced by the mesophyll cells lacking GDC activity. The second possible reason is that the GDC is both knocked down in mesophyll and bundle sheath cells, either thru the loss of mesophyll preferential expression of the ZmPEPC promoter or the leakage of the mature amiGDCP from the

adjacent mesophyll cells. The second reason is easier to prove and resolve compared to the first one.

Miss-expression can be easily determined through immuno-localization given a monoclonal antibody or by in-situ hybridization to assess the tissue specific expression of GDCP; unfortunately both techniques were not done in this study. The miss-expression can be easily resolved by over-expressing the native GDCP gene using a bundle sheath specific promoter and introduce a same sense mutation in the exon targeted by the amiGDCP construct. Rice bundle sheath specific promoters have already been characterized and complementation of amiRNA constructs is possible (Schuler et al., 2016; Warthmann et al., 2008).

The first possible reason can be inferred from the basic rice leaf anatomy which is a quantitative trait. Evolution of C_4 syndrome through the formation of transitional states suggest that C_2 -Kranz anatomy must be installed first before the establishment of C_2 photosynthesis or technically the relocation of GDC from the mesophyll cells into the bundle sheath cells (Monson & Rawsthorne, 2000; R. F. Sage et al., 2012). If the first hypothesis is correct, then the result of this study supports the theory that establishment of the C_2 -Kranz anatomy must happen before the relocation of the GDC.

The glycine is produced from the transamination of the glyoxylate product of the C_2 cycle. The accumulation of high glycine amounts come with a concomitant depletion of other amino acids that serves as the amino donor of the transamination reaction. The

effect on the possible amino acids that could serve as amino donor for the amination of glyoxylate was also analyzed and shown in Figure 37. Serine and alanine can serve as substrates for serine:glyoxylate transaminase (SGT), while glutamate is the substrate for glutamate:glyoxylate transaminase (GGT) which is regenerated in the GS-GOGAT cycle with glutamine as an intermediate (Forde & Lea, 2007; Igarashi et al., 2003; Liepman & Olsen, 2001). Glutamate and glutamine values were significantly reduced in plants grown in ambient condition as predicted due to high photorespiration. Though, glutamate and glutamine were depleted in the wildtype grown ICU condition, which could be due to higher nitrogen requirement of plants grown in high CO₂ condition (Stitt & Krapp, 1999). Interestingly alanine values of the knockdown lines were not significantly different from wildtype and maintained at significantly low amounts in the growing two conditions, except IRS896-3 plants which were grown in ICU. Aspartate could also be a potential indirect amino donor of glyoxylate thru glutamate via aspartate aminotransferase, as observed in the significant reductions found in the transgenic lines compared to wild type plants. The complete list of amino acids is in Table 4.

Figure 37. Some of the leaf soluble amino acids of the IRS896 lines subjected to high CO₂ (ICU) and ambient air conditions. (**A** and **B**) Glutamate and alanine are two other amino donors of glyoxylate to produce glycine. (**C** and **D**) Glutamine and aspartic acid showed significant reductions in the knockdown lines except glutamine values in ICU.

Table 4. Leaf soluble amino acids ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of dry weight) analyzed for IRS896, IRS897, and wild type plants subjected to high CO_2 and ambient air conditions. Due to the number of amino acids with values close to the limit of detection, one-way ANOVA was not applicable for statistical analysis. Instead, the non-parametric equivalent Kruskal-Wallis test on ranks was used and Dunn's test was used for post-hoc multiple pairwise comparison. SE = standard error ($\alpha=0.05$).

Amino Acid	896-1	896-3	WT	896-1	896-3	WT
Condition	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient	ICU	ICU	ICU
Gly/Ser Ratio	80.36	*132.84	0.47	55.11	119.00	2.12
SE	30.04	29.82	0.29	14.13	20.20	0.36
Aspartic Acid	*0.00	*0.00	0.42	*0.03	*0.02	2.13
SE	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.02	0.02	0.32
Glutamic Acid	0.26	0.24	2.41	0.20	0.07	0.08
SE	0.18	0.14	0.17	0.10	0.05	0.02
Asparagine	0.15	0.34	0.08	*0.00	*0.00	0.98
SE	0.08	0.12	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.09
Histidine	0.47	1.07	0.00	0.08	0.21	0.05
SE	0.47	0.67	0.00	0.08	0.21	0.05
Serine	0.20	0.13	0.22	0.13	0.08	0.11
SE	0.09	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.01
Glutamine	0.09	*0.08	1.29	0.13	0.02	0.00
SE	0.09	0.08	0.33	0.03	0.02	0.00
Arginine	0.27	0.98	0.02	0.03	0.13	0.19
SE	0.27	0.63	0.01	0.03	0.13	0.06
Glycine	*12.13	*14.83	0.09	6.19	*9.43	0.22
SE	1.65	3.77	0.05	0.54	1.08	0.03
Threonine	0.40	0.38	0.15	0.23	0.43	0.01
SE	0.25	0.23	0.01	0.02	0.16	0.01
Tyrosine	0.17	0.62	0.23	0.27	0.08	0.17
SE	0.17	0.32	0.23	0.27	0.08	0.17
Alanine	0.05	0.04	0.15	0.15	*0.37	0.02
SE	0.05	0.02	0.08	0.05	0.02	0.02
GABA	0.00	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.01	0.01
SE	0.00	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.01
Tryptophan	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SE	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Methionine	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
SE	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
Valine	0.32	0.00	0.04	0.68	1.36	0.00
SE	0.17	0.00	0.04	0.35	0.88	0.00
Phenylalanine	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.29	0.24	0.00
SE	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.07	0.17	0.00
Isoleucine	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.15	0.00
SE	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.15	0.00
Leucine	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.02	*0.28	0.00
SE	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.00
Lysine	0.67	0.18	0.00	0.10	0.35	0.00
SE	0.67	0.18	0.00	0.10	0.16	0.00

Carbohydrate profile of could also explain the changes in photosynthetic capacities of the plants. Figure 34 shows the soluble sugar and starch contents in the leaves of GDCP knockdown plants compared to wild type plants grown in two different growing conditions. The accumulation of glycine in the knockdown plants does not only alter nitrogen pools but carbon balance in the leaves as well. The production of photorespiratory glycine which cannot be decarboxylated in the GDCP knockdown lines drains the C_3 cycle of necessary photosynthates for the production carbohydrates (Stefan Timm et al., 2012). Plants grown in ICU had higher soluble sugars and starch content compared to the ones grown in ambient, which is explained by the lower photorespiratory stress (S. H. Cheng et al., 1998; Sun et al., 2002). Both transgenic events had significantly lower sucrose and starch content even at ICU condition where starch degradation during the day is reduced (Stitt & Krapp, 1999; Weise, 2006). The results suggest the possible impact of glycine accumulation with the carbohydrate metabolism in GDCP knockdown lines. Altered carbohydrate metabolism can also be explained by the changes in the photosynthetic capacity of the knockdown lines.

Figure 38. Soluble sugars and starch content of the GDCP knockdown lines in different CO₂ concentration growing condition. All the soluble sugars (A, B, and C) and starch (D) samples were collected from the same tissue samples.

Changes in Photosynthetic Capacity

A good measure of photorespiratory impaired phenotype is if the plant's O₂ sensitivity during leaf gas exchange measurement was still retained (Blackwell et al., 1988). Rice photosynthesis increases as a response with reducing the O₂ concentration during the gas exchange measurement (Sage and Khoshravesh, 2016). Reduction of O₂ leads to decrease in photorespiration thereby increasing the overall CO₂ assimilation rate. A C₄ plant such maize generally does not have significant effect on photosynthesis when O₂ concentration is reduced below ambient conditions due to its low rate of photorespiration (G. Edwards & Walker, 1983; Maroco et al., 1998).

Figure 39 shows photosynthetic rate of GDGP knockdown lines at 21% (ambient) and 2% O₂. Rate of CO₂ assimilation was measured at a light intensity of 2000 μmol of photons $\text{m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, CO₂ concentration was maintained at 400 $\mu\text{mol mol air}^{-1}$, and leaf temperature of 30°C. Wild type plants display the typical significant increase in CO₂ assimilation rate when O₂ was reduced to 2%. It is also worth noting that wild type plants grown in ICU had lower CO₂ assimilation rate compared to plants grown in ambient condition. Plants grown in saturating CO₂ concentration (more than 2000 ppm) for a long period of time tend to suffer from lower photosynthetic rates compared to plants grown in ambient due to higher nitrogen demand. Carbohydrate accumulation especially hexoses, in plants grown in ICU tend to down regulate the Rubisco expression, hence the observed lower CO₂ assimilation rates of wildtype grown in ICU (S. H. Cheng et al., 1998). Both

events of IRS896 grown in ICU had no significant reduction in CO₂ assimilation rate which correlates to the low sucrose content even in ICU described earlier.

All of the plants exhibited O₂ sensitivity which showed an increase in CO₂ assimilation rate when O₂ was reduced. Reduction of O₂ favors carboxylation of Rubisco which increases the rate of RuBP regeneration, the acceptor of CO₂, ultimately increasing the rate of CO₂ assimilation. The instantaneous gas exchange measurements were done at 0.04 % CO₂ (ambient) while the O₂ was being measured at 21% (ambient) and 2%. Table 5 shows the summary of the assimilation rates presented in Figure 39. Both IRS896 events showed significantly lower CO₂ assimilation rates compared to wild type plants when grown in both ICU and ambient conditions.

The IRS896 plants' very low CO₂ assimilation rates in ambient CO₂ concentration (0.04%) and ambient O₂ concentration (21%) depicts the photosynthetic performance of the plants grown in ambient for eight days. The observed values show that they are barely performing photosynthesis at 0.6-1 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in the ambient compared to wildtype that have around 30 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ which explains the chlorosis and early senescence phenotype. Even when the O₂ concentration was reduced to 2%, the net photosynthesis was still significantly lower than the wildtype grown in the same condition.

The CO₂ assimilation rates of the transgenic lines both grown in ICU or ambient, and measured at 2% or 21% O₂ were still significantly lower compared to wildtype. The results indicates that at 0.04% ambient CO₂ concentration regardless of O₂ concentration,

the GDCP knockdown lines had significant impact on rate of photosynthesis presumably through high photorepiratory rates (Engel et al., 2007).

Figure 39. Instantaneous gas exchange measurement of net CO₂ assimilation rates in response to decreasing oxygen concentration of the GDCP knockdown lines subjected to different CO₂ growing conditions. CO₂ assimilation rate at 21% O₂ was measured as the average assimilation rate after 5 mins of acclimation and then shifted to 2% O₂ for 10 mins. CO₂ assimilation rate at 2% O₂ was measured at the maximum assimilation rate in the span of 10 mins in 2% O₂. Rate of CO₂ assimilation was measured at a light intensity of 2000 µmol of photons m⁻²s⁻¹, CO₂ concentration was maintained at 400 µmol mol air⁻¹, and leaf temperature of 30°C.

Table 5. Summary of CO₂ assimilation rate with response to oxygen concentration of T1 GDCP knockdown lines subjected to ambient and ICU condition. All of the plants analyzed showed significant difference in *A* between 21% and 2% O₂. One-way ANOVA ($\alpha=0.05$), LSD used for pairwise mean comparison, means with the same letter is not statistically significant.

CO ₂ assimilation rate, <i>A</i>		
Ambient	21% O ₂ ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$)	2% O ₂ ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$)
IRS896-1	1.06±0.27 ^b	7.28±0.73 ^b
IRS896-3	0.6±0.23 ^b	5.26±0.43 ^b
Wildtype	30.88±1.09 ^a	41.43±1.52 ^a
ICU		
IRS896-1	3.28±1.52 ^b	14.34±2.99 ^b
IRS896-3	0.21±0.11 ^b	4.03±0.52 ^c
Wildtype	26.68±0.86 ^a	36.72±0.82 ^a

To further analyze the effect of O₂ in CO₂ assimilation rate of the GDCP knockdown plants, full A/Ci curves in different O₂ treatments was performed the next day (Fig. 40). The response of the two events were similar based on the instantaneous gas exchange measurement, therefore only the IRS896-1 was selected for the full A/Ci measurement. Also only the plants maintained in the ICU were measured for full A/Ci measurement due lack of good leaves (non-senescing) to measure in the plants exposed to ambient air for nine days.

Figure 40 show the full A/Ci curves of IRS896-1 and wild type plants. A good measure of CO₂ concentrating mechanism is through the computation of CO₂ compensation point (Γ) in an A/Ci curve, which also indicates the efficiency of photorespiration (Krenzer et al., 1975; Vogán et al., 2007). The CO₂ assimilation rate observed at the ambient CO₂ (400ppm) and ambient O₂ (21%) in the previous experiment were similar to values plotted in the ACi curve presented. IRS896-1 had significantly

different Γ of $190 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ compared to wild type around $58 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ which showed almost four fold increase (Figs. 23). The Γ of IRS896 T₁ plants were slightly lower than those of the T₀ plants which could be explained by the tissue culture effect.

Γ can be interpreted as the minimum amount of intercellular CO₂ concentration (C_i, CO₂ in the intercellular spaces in the leaves) needed for CO₂ assimilation to occur (Osmond, 1981). C_i is dependent on ambient CO₂ concentration (C_a) and the stomatal conductance. The stomatal conductance of the IRS896 observed in the measurement at 400 ppm C_a was twofold lower than the wildtype, which means that the stomatal opening is almost shut. This implies that IRS896 plants were barely performing photosynthesis when grown at ambient, which could have implied the photorespiratory mutant phenotype observed. After the O₂ concentration was shifted from 21% to 2%, the CO₂ assimilation rate and stomatal conductance became similar to the wild type values at 21% O₂ (Fig. 40C). Photorespiration has been observed to have control in stomatal regulation (Igamberdiev et al., 2004). The fast response of the stomatal opening during the reduction of O₂ shows the dynamic regulation of photorespiration in response to changing O₂ concentration.

The CO₂ assimilation rate of IRS896 at ambient O₂ concentration (21%) show a linear increase as the C_i increases without plateauing (Fig. 40A). The C_a at the highest C_i value for IRS896-1 at 21% O₂ was already 2000 ppm and yet it still not saturated unlike

the wildtype values. This evidence explains why the IRS896 can survive and mature in ICU condition which has super saturating CO₂ concentration of 10,000 ppm.

Figure 40. CO₂ assimilation rates (A) in response to intercellular CO₂ concentration (C_i) curve of the IRS896 and IRS897 selected lines that showed the lowest CO₂ assimilation rate in the instantaneous gas exchange measurement. (A) Full AC_i curves were measured at 21% O₂ and 2% O₂ of selected GDCP knockdown plants grown in ICU only (~10,000 μmol CO₂ mol air⁻¹). Measurements were made at light intensity of 2,000 μmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹ and a leaf temperature of 30°C. (B) Rate of CO₂ assimilation at a reference CO₂ input of 20, 50, 100, and 200 μmol mol air⁻¹. (C) Rate of CO₂ assimilation at a reference CO₂ input of 1000, 1200, 1500, and 2000 μmol mol air⁻¹.

The light response curve presents the net CO₂ assimilation with response to varying light intensities (Ogren & Evans, 1993). Similar trend was observed in the T₀ and T₁ LRC of the IRS896 plants.

The GDCP knockdown line and wild type plants showed no significant difference in quantum efficiencies (QE) (Fig. 41B). Quantum efficiency (QE) or quantum yield is measured as the linear slope of the initial points in the LRC. QE is defined as the amount of O₂ evolved or CO₂ consumed per photon of light absorbed (Emerson, 1958). It assesses the state of the light harvesting part of photosynthesis and its active interaction with the CO₂ fixing part of photosynthesis in the early stages of exposure to light (Sharp et al., 1984). Similar QE observed for IRS896 and wildtype indicates that light harvesting and CO₂ fixing part of photosynthesis is still intact for the GDCP knockdown plants. However, GDCP knockdown plants had significantly lower light saturation point or the maximum irradiance where photosynthesis peaked (Kull & Kruijt, 1998). This phenomena indicates photoinhibition which is associated to impaired photorespiration through the suppression of repair of photosystem II but not the acceleration of damage processes (Takahashi et al., 2007). To confirm the status of the photosystem II in the GDCP knockdown plants fluorescence measurement was done.

Figure 41. Light response curves of selected IRS896 and IRS897 GDCP knockdown lines. **(A)** Rate of CO₂ assimilation in response to changing irradiance. **(B)** The initial points in the light curve that were used to calculate the quantum efficiency (Q.E.). Measurements were made at 400 ppm C_a and a leaf temperature of 30°C and photosynthesis were measured at light intensity of 20 to 2,000 μmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹.

Fv/Fm serves as measure of quantum efficiency of photosystem II or the oxygen-evolving complex. It is measured through the use of portable pulse amplitude modulated (PAM) fluorimeters with dark adaptation of the leaves (PAM 2500, Walz, Effeltrich, Germany). The GDCP knockdown lines showed no significant difference in Fv/Fm

values compared to wild type plants (Fig. 42A). This result implies that the change in photosynthetic rates is not a result of defective photosystem II but might be due to the effect of photorespiratory metabolites on the dynamic damage and repair of photosystem II during photosynthesis (Takahashi et al., 2007).

Through leaf fluorescence measurement, GDCP knockdown lines also showed significant increase in rates of dark respiration which might be due to the physiological stress brought by impaired photorespiration. It could also be due to decarboxylation of excess accumulated glycine during the day by the remaining active GDCP even in the dark (Fig. 42B). If the latter reason is correct, it implies that there is still an absence of efficient recapture of photorespired CO₂.

Figure 42. Chlorophyll fluorescence measurements of selected GDCP knockdown lines. **(A)** Reduced Fv/Fm measurement indicates GDCP knockdown affects photosystem II in a dark adapted state. **(B)** Rate of dark respiration measured at the middle of the day with leaf dark adapted for 20 mins, CO₂ concentration was maintained at 400 µmol mol air⁻¹, and leaf temperature of 30°C.

Severe Photorespiratory Phenotype

Studies of the known photorespiratory mutants from different species show that the phenotype varies from wildtype-like, mild, and severe sensitivity to ambient O₂ depending on what part of the cycle was perturbed or if the protein plays other important roles in primary metabolism (S. Timm & Bauwe, 2013; Wingler et al., 2000). It was also shown that most of the C₂ cycle gene knockout mutants that produce mild or wildtype-like photorespiratory phenotype contain more than one copy that leads to complementing effect to compensate the loss of the paralogous knocked-out gene (Timm and Bauwe, 2013). The importance of GDCP in primary metabolism to ensure plant survival, and having several gene copies in most plant species, had become difficult to identify severe photorepiratory phenotype thru conventional mutant screening (Engel et al., 2007; Fernie et al., 2013). This study is the first of its kind to observe severe photorespiratory phenotype in GDCP knockdown plant by using tissue specific gene silencing approach to target two genes in the leaves simultaneously.

To show the severe photorepiratory phenotype of the IRS896 a simple experiment of growing single copy homozygous plants in ambient air. Azygous plants, used as a control, are homozygous recessive for the amiGDCP gene copy (no transgene present) which is similar to wildtype but came from IRS896 heterozygous parent. IRS896-3 three gene copies produced a single copy offspring at T₁ generation and were advanced to homozygosity in T₃ generation. T₃ homozygous and azygous plants were germinated and grown in standard growing conditions.

Figure 43 to figure 46 show the documentation of IRS896-3 single copy homozygous and azygous lines and the progression of severe photorespiratory phenotype. At 7 days after germination (DAG), the photorespiratory impaired phenotype was not apparent but the homozygous plants were noticeably smaller to azygous (Fig. 43A). At 14 DAG the chlorosis and stunted growth of the homozygous plants are now evident (Fig. 43B). At 18 DAG plants were transferred into 0.5L pots. Apart from chlorosis and stunted growth, early senescence of the older leaves is clearly observed in the homozygous plants (Fig. 44). At 25 DAG the azygous plants have produced two to three tillers while the homozygous plants still have only one (Fig. 45). Azygous plants were significantly taller than the homozygous. The homozygous plants show progressive leaf senescence from the oldest to the youngest fully emerged leaf (Fig. 46). At 45 DAG homozygous plants show no signs of recovery when grown in ambient air.

Figure 43. Phenotype of IRS896-3 single copy homozygous and azygous lines in T_3 generation grown in ambient condition. (A) show seedlings in hydroponics at seven days after germination (DAG). (B) show same seedlings in hydroponics at 14 DAG. Homozygous and azygous plants were interspaced between one another.

Figure 44. Phenotype of IRS896-3 single copy homozygous and azygous lines in T_3 generation grown in ambient condition showing photorespiratory impaired phenotype at 18 DAG in 0.5L pots. (A) shows the photorespiratory phenotype of homozygous lines at 18 DAG. (B) shows the corresponding azygous (wildtype like) lines in (A).

Figure 45. Phenotype of IRS896-3 single copy homozygous and azygous lines in T_3 generation grown in ambient condition showing photorespiratory impaired phenotype at 25 DAG in 0.5L pots. (A) and (B) are the same plants presented in Figure 43 at 25 DAG showing more pronounced photorespiratory phenotype.

Figure 46. Close up images of IRS896-3 T₃ lines showing clear photorespiratory phenotype of homozygous single copy lines compared to azygous lines at 25 DAG (A). (B) and (C) are close up images showing stunted growth, chlorosis, and early senescence.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Photorespiration or C_2 cycle is an energy wasteful but important pathway for plants to grow in oxygen rich environment as a consequence of the oxygenase activity of Rubisco. Plants have evolved to minimize the oxygenase activity of Rubisco through concentrating mechanism called C_4 photosynthesis. Through a stepwise evolution the C_2 cycle was co-opted as a CO_2 concentrating mechanism called C_2 photosynthesis which provided a transitional state to C_4 photosynthesis. C_2 photosynthesis has been one of the landmark traits of C_3 - C_4 intermediate species where it has been deemed as part of the initial steps in the evolution of C_4 photosynthesis. The early analysis of the C_3 - C_4 intermediate species identified that the relocation of the glycine decarboxylation from the mesophyll cells to the bundle sheath cells is the main driver for the establishment of C_2 photosynthesis. This study attempted to mimic the relocation of the glycine decarboxylation through knocking-down the GDCP component of the glycine decarboxylase complex in the mesophyll cells of rice.

The results of this study have proven that the GDCP was successfully knocked down in rice leaves using artificial microRNA. Only IRS896 demonstrated significant reduction of transcript and undetectable protein expression of the two isoforms in rice out of the two constructs that was created. The protein reduction was supported by the accumulation of glycine and changes in other metabolite concentration typical of photorespiratory mutant.

The transgenic events from IRS896 had the best GDCP knockdown and showed classical photorespiratory impaired phenotype of suffering from pronounced early senescence and chlorosis when grown in ambient air however recover when placed in high CO₂ condition (ICU, 0.01%). The strong photorespiratory phenotype was complemented by several gas exchange measurement that show reduced photosynthetic activity.

Detailed analysis of the two events of IRS896 in T1 generation was done to characterize the effect on photorespiration. Since the IRS896 lines were grown in ICU, the effect of high photorespiratory rates were observed by subjecting half of the population in ambient air for several days. The GDCP knockdown plants grown in ambient air or ICU both have undetectable levels of GDCP protein expression compared to wildtype. The different growing condition produced similar photorespiratory mutant responses on metabolites and photosynthetic measurements of the GDCP knockdown lines that were significantly different compared to wildtype. Knockdown lines grown in ambient air had higher photorepiratory stress compared to the ones grown in ICU. Oxygen sensitivity was still evident in the knockdown lines, with 2% O₂ significantly restore the photosynthetic capacity similar to the wildtype in ambient. Fluorescence measurements also indicate that the cause of the reduced photosynthesis is due to the accumulation of photorespiratory metabolites that slows down CO₂ assimilation.

All molecular and physiological analyses done in this study all point to the fact that knocking down GDCP in rice mesophyll cells is not enough to induce C₂

photosynthesis. The occurrence of the rice C_3 leaf anatomy having numerous mesophyll cells containing a lot of chloroplasts compared to the bundle sheath cells implies that most of the photosynthesis happens in the mesophyll cells. Producing an efficient knockdown of most GDCP in the mesophyll cells would generate a great amount of glycine pool, but the remaining GDCP in the few bundle sheath cell mitochondria could not keep up with rate of photorespiration in ambient air, exhibited by the huge increase in compensation point and creating a conditional lethal phenotype.

The study was limited by the lack of evidence to prove that the GDCP was still active in the bundle sheath cells. Immuno-localization of the P-protein was not possible since the anti-body obtained is not monoclonal. Unfortunately in-situ hybridization of the transcript or tissue specific isolation was not done. The ability of the IRS896 plants to still survive in ICU could imply that there still some remaining GDC activity to metabolize glycine in manageable levels. It would be interesting to know if the glycine accumulated during the day would somehow be processed by the few remaining GDC activity or by protein synthesis at night.

The C_2 -Kranz anatomy that is shared by most C_3 - C_4 intermediate species is believed as one of the earliest potentiating change in C_3 anatomy towards C_4 evolution, even earlier than the establishment of C_2 photosynthesis. Without the C_2 -Kranz anatomy first in place, it seems that greatly reducing the GDCP in the mesophyll of rice simply produce a classical photorespiratory impaired phenotype rather than inducing C_2 photosynthesis.

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